

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

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D8.3 3D Subsurface Visualisations of the Lock Walls and Foundation

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/ Term	Description
BDO	Base de données des ouvrages (VNF's Infrastructure Database)
BPF	Band Pass Filtering
CMMS	Computerised Maintenance Management System (at VNF)
DT	Digital Twin
DXF	Interactive 3D structures (data format)
FCI	Functional Condition Index
FoI	Feature of Interest (subsurface, within the asset structure or surrounding earthwork)
GA	Grant Agreement
GER	Gros Entretien Renouvellement (Major Maintenance and Renewal)
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System (coordinates/antenna/etc.)
GPR	Ground Penetrating Radar
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format 5 (an open-source file format for storing and managing large, complex datasets)
IWW	Inland Water Way
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation (type of file)
PCC	Control Centre (at VNF)
Prism2	Proprietary radar control software
SEG-Y / SEG-Y	Society of Exploration Geophysicists Files (type of files generated by GPR equipment)
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar (system)
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator coordinates
VNF	Voies navigables de France (the French navigation authority responsible for the management of the majority of France's inland waterways)
VTO	Visiteurs Techniques d'Ouvrage (Technical inspection/inspector of an asset, at VNF)
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

The goal of this deliverable is to present the methodology developed for, and outcomes of generating visualisation of the scan data acquired from the testing of the Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) system in the French River Pilot.

The CRISTAL project aims to develop technological strategies to increase the modal share of inland waterway freight by 20%, improve its reliability by 80%, and maintain 50% operational capacity during extreme weather events. The use of the SIR system in general, and visualisation of the scan results in particular, can potentially contribute to this through the improved knowledge of the condition of assets facilitating:

- The improvement of the efficiency and effectiveness of the maintenance process, reducing operating costs and disruption.
- The reduction of the risk of unexpected failure of assets due to undetected defects, which might be exposed in extreme weather events.
- The improvement of the reliability of the IWW network contributing to attractiveness of IWW transport, and therefore modal shift.

The SIR system was tested at three locations in the French River Pilot that are described in this deliverable in order to provide context for associating the visualisations of the subsurface conditions generated from the scan results with the configuration of the asset as apparent on site. The test sites selected by VNF are three locks where there are suspected to be subsurface issues and provide a variety of location types, one broad gauge lock and two narrow gauge locks, for testing the SIR system.

The objective of the deliverable is to provide a detailed set of visualisations generated from the SIR scan results, alongside describing the process of generating the visualisations, that can be used to inform managers of the subsurface condition of the IWW assets scanned. The further objective is to discuss the potential for the integration of scanning large IWW assets with the SIR system to be integrated into the asset management and maintenance processes of the assets and potentially contribute to the improvement of the efficiency and effectiveness of the maintenance process and the reliability of the IWW network.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 provides an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable and corresponding task's descriptions included in the grant agreement (GA) along with the relevant justifications regarding how the D8.3 and Task 8.4 objectives have been achieved.

Table 1: Alignment of D8.3 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification/ Details
DELIVERABLE			
D8.3 3D subsurface visualisations	D8.3 will provide 3D subsurface visualisations of the	Sections 1 to 3.3, Section	Sections 1 to 3.3 introduce the generation of the visualisations, provide context for interpreting

of the lock walls and foundation	lock walls and foundation ...	4, and appendices	them, and display the results for the tests. Section 4 summarises conclusions about the process of generating the visualisations and the visualisations generated in the tests. Appendices include additional details, in particular graphical representations of visualisations achieved.
	...to support the modernisation programme.	Section 3.4 and Section 4	Section 3.4 describes the potential integration of the visualisations in maintenance and asset management processes. Section 4 includes conclusions about the potential use of the visualisations for asset management.
TASKS			
Task 8.4 Tools for predictive infrastructure maintenance	This inspection system will then be used for the inspection of the infrastructure in the French Pilot. EUMO will collect the data... It is also possible that small inland waterway locks may be included in the inspection trials as they are thought to be in need of repair.	Section 3 (subsections 3.1.1, 3.2.1 and 3.3.1)	Within Section 3, the collection of data for each lock scanned is described within the relevant subsection for each lock.
	UNEW will provide 3D subsurface visualisations of the lock walls and foundation.	Sections 1 to 3.3, and Appendices	These sections introduce the generation of the visualisations, provide context for interpreting them, and display the results for the tests.
and VNF will use this information to support the modernisation program.	Section 3.4 and Section 4	Section 3.4 describes the potential integration of the visualisations in maintenance and asset management process.

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Deliverable 8.3 is divided in four mains sections, with additional supporting information included in the appendices.

Section 1 Executive Summary, i.e., the current one, introduces first (§1.1) the deliverable in the context of the CRISTAL project, in general, and of work package (WP) 8 River Pilot France, in particular. The objective of the work reported in the deliverable is clearly defined, along with the specific activities carried out to reach the objective.

Then, the content of the report is mapped against relevant tasks in the CRISTAL project, and deliverables reporting the outcomes of those specific tasks (§1.2).

The current subsection (§1.3) provides more details about the structure and the content of this deliverable report.

Section 2 Describes the methodology for Visualisation of SIR Survey data, including:

- An overview of the SIR technology and data collection process, along with the structure and format developed for organised storage and access of the data.
- The method for analysing the raw data and generating the 3D spatial profile of radar return values.
- The process of identifying and characterising features of interest in the scanned volume from the data.
- An overview of the processed used for quality assurance of the methodology for collecting and processing scanned data, based on simulations and comparisons of laboratory-based scans of volumes with a known structure.
- A description of the different files and views in the standardised package of multimedia output files generated from the SIR scan data, for end-user to visualise and interpret the results.

Section 3 describes the results of the tests of the SIR system carried out within the French River Pilot, specifically scans carried out on and around three lock structures. Within this section, for each lock scanned, an overview is given of the lock to provide context for the results, then the most relevant multimedia files for visualising features identified in the scan results are presented for the lock wall and surroundings, where applicable, of that lock. Following the results a discussion of the interpretation of the scan results in terms of the potential information they contain about the condition of the lock structure is presented, along with how that information could potentially be used in maintenance processes.

In **Section 4**, conclusions and recommendations are made about the SIR scanning system visualisation process, the results obtained in the tests, and the potential use of this type data collection and information in maintenance processes for large IWW structures.

In the **Appendices**, additional multimedia files generated to visualise the scan results are presented to show the fuller range of visualisation outputs available, and as supporting information.

2. Methodology for Visualisation of SIR Survey Data

This section outlines the methodology for processing and visualising SIR (Subsurface Inspection Radar) survey data. Section 2.1 provides an overview of the SIR technology and data acquisition process. Section 2.2 details the data analytics workflow, followed by the approach to feature analysis in Section 2.3. Quality assurance procedures are addressed in Section 2.4. Finally, Section 2.5 summarises the steps for generating multimedia output files.

2.1. Overview of technology and data collection

2.1.1. Overview of SIR System

A comprehensive presentation of SIR system design was provided in Deliverable D2.2 (CRISTAL, 2024a).

The SIR system was developed to examine the subsurface condition of key structural assets within the European Inland Waterways network, primarily the sheer vertical concrete walls integral to lock infrastructure. Conducting SIR surveys of these structures and their immediate surroundings, and integrating the results within the digital twin (DT), is proposed as a viable approach to enhancing the long-term resilience of the network.

Key challenges included the development of a system capable of inspecting the subsurface of large-scale, sheer vertical concrete walls up to 10m in height and spanning over 100m in length, alongside the processing of survey data to return clear visualisations of subsurface defects and associated geometries. This was achieved by leveraging recent advances in 3D visualisation of Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) datasets.

The developed SIR system combined a bespoke physical hardware platform, comprising state-of-the-art radar technology, integrated with a dedicated motorised positioning frame and a software-driven data analytics workflow responsible for converting raw radar measurement data into more intuitive 3D spatial profiles of subsurface Features of Interest¹ (Fols), with a primary focus on the detection and characterisation of voids.

In addition, the radar equipment was deployed and tested using a simple set-up (the radar being mounted on a cart operated manually) for scanning specific surroundings of the lock for detecting potential Fols within the earthworks adjacent to the lock structures.

2.1.2. Overview of SIR Data Collection

The SIR data collection procedure was semi-automated. The system utilised stepper motors on each movement axis to enable precise and predictable linear motion of the radar antenna sensor along each transect² scan trajectory. This motion was governed by a pre-defined sequence of motor commands, that could be triggered sequentially by a human operator if required.

A mobile crane was positioned adjacent to the lock, maintaining a safe distance from both the lock edge and the survey team. The SIR frame was secured to the crane using ropes and straps.

¹ These represent any subsurface anomaly detected, considered sufficiently significant to warrant closer attention and possible intervention, subject to context.

² A transect is a survey pass, by operating/moving the radar from a position to another, which generates a 2D cross section of the subsurface.

By extending the crane's boom, the frame could be safely manoeuvred over the lock edge and its centre aligned with that of the current survey quadrant (pre-marked on the lock side using spray paint). Vertical positioning of the frame along the wall was achieved by unwinding the winch line. This operation was supported by a spotter stationed on the opposite side of the lock, who monitored the frame's vertical alignment and provided real-time feedback to the crane operator. Additional ropes attached to either side of the frame enabled fine-tuning of its position and helped minimise frame twisting during descent. Once in place, the boom was retracted to bring the frame's stand-off feet into contact with the wall surface, temporarily securing it for the duration of the quadrant survey.

Once the frame was in position, the radar antenna was moved to its home position in the upper-left corner of the frame (as viewed from the opposite side of the lock). During a survey pass, the antenna followed a serpentine scanning pattern. The first half of this pattern was composed of sequential horizontal transects—each aligned parallel to the lock edge. The antenna advanced in alternating directions (away from and toward the home position), with each transect spaced at intervals of 0.114m. Upon reaching the lower-right corner of the frame, the antenna was rotated 90 degrees so that its longest side was perpendicular to the lock edge. The second half of the serpentine scan pattern performed a similar scanning sequence, this time in the vertical direction, again with alternating scan directions and consistent spacing of 0.135m between sequential transects. Completion of the vertical scans returned the antenna back to its home position, where it was rotated back to its original orientation, ready for the crane to reposition the frame at the next quadrant location. This sequence was repeated throughout the duration of the survey window and, in a complete structural assessment, would be conducted across the full extent of both lock walls.

Transect data was acquired using Prism2 radar control software. Subsurface response data was recorded continuously during each independent transect as the antenna was advanced across the wall. Data recording was paused when moving the antenna between successive transects. The direction of antenna advanced was alternated on each successive transect to maximise data collection efficiency. Note that any data recorded with reversed direction of travel was reversed during subsequent data processing. Transect measurements and motor operation were manually triggered by the operator via keystrokes. To avoid truncation of transects, data capture was initiated slightly before antenna movement commenced and continued briefly after the antenna reached its maximum displacement along each respective axis of motion. These overspill regions were cropped during processing to retain only valid subsurface measurements. Although various automated keystroke triggering methods were explored during development, manual control was selected as the optimal balance between operational efficiency and adaptability.

2.1.3. SIR Survey Data Format and Structure

SIR data collection, processing and output generation involves multiple data formats.

While a single, standardised data format across the full system architecture was initially desired (e.g., HDF5 or JSON) for cross compatibility between SIR subsystems and synchronisation with the DT, respectively, this proved impractical. In part, this was due to the inherently restricted nature of radar software – typically reliant on manufacturer-specific filetypes such as:

- Society of Exploration Geophysicists Files (SEG-Y / .SEG-Y | Multiple³)

³ Whilst, in principle, an international interchangeable data format, manufacturers may add additional non-standard data block(s), preventing files from been recognised by other programs.

- Data Trace Files (DT1/RD7/HD | e.g., MALA)
- Data Zipped Files (DTZ| e.g., GSSI)
- Radar Data Files (RAD| e.g., IDS Georadar)
- Ground Penetrating Radar File (GPR| e.g., gprMax, GPRpy)

Figure 1: SIR raw data: SEG-Y - transect measurements

In addition, radar survey data is inherently multidimensional, necessitating generation of a diverse range of outputs of different types (with associated data formats) to enable informed interpretations of measurement data to be drawn. Data types and formats include, but are not limited to:

- Static 2D imagery (PNG | e.g., planar projections, satellite overlays, individual depth slices)
- Pseudo-planar 2.5D visuals (PNG | e.g., isometric projections, multi-slices)
- Interactive 3D structures (DXF | e.g., 3D objects)
- Moving animations (MP4| e.g., sequential depth slicing, orbitals)
- Plain text files (TXT/HTML | e.g., metadata files, summary files)

Ultimately, the use of multiple data formats was essential in order to provide the most contextually appropriate and streamlined solution for information storage and manipulation, subject to context (i.e., the specific portion of SIR architecture considered).

Pre-requisite data encompassed: lock specifications; survey brief; list(s) of available facilities; relevant maintenance information and details of the physical structure undergoing inspection (see D2.2). This information was communicated ahead of SIR tests(s) on the French River Pilot through email exchanges between UNEW, EUMO and VNF, stored in the cloud as MSG data files, or locally, where required, as PDF files. Notably, VNF provided copies of lock design documents, which gave an overview of key structural elements (e.g., cross-sectional profile, water drainage tunnel dimensions) and relevant associated characteristics (e.g., estimated wall thicknesses, depths and rebar properties) of typical Inland Waterway lock structures.

As described in deliverable D2.3 (CRISTAL, 2025a), radar data collection was facilitated through a Zond 12e Advanced Radar controller connected to a PC running Prism2 software, which triggered and saved radar measurements, throughout. Raw measurements were encoded in SEG-Y (SGY)

files as binary data in Little-Endian format, which has $ab_H = 3600$ byte EBCDIC⁴ global header block. Files also contained an additional (non SEG-Y standard) $b_{H_p} = 692$ byte descriptive preamble in plain text. Individual radar trace⁵ measurements were divided $b_h = 240$ byte local headers, followed by $b_t = 256$ byte amplitude data blocks (Figure 2). For a given trace measurement, the corresponding starting byte index (b_{start}) of the relevant data block $B_{i \in [0,1,\dots,N-1]}$ was given by $b_{start} = b_H + i(b_h + 2b_t)$.

Figure 2: SIR processed data file formats: (a) PNG - 2D imagery; (b) MP4 – video footage; (c) DXF – 3D objects; (d) TXT/HTML – metadata and summary files

⁴ Extended Binary Coded Decimal Interchange Code.

⁵ 1D radar measurement of signal backscatter intensity against two-way travel time (i.e. depth).

These files were processed using the SIR data management subsystem (see D2.2), returning aforementioned output data formats - visually summarised in Figure 2. Where a choice of file formats was available, the more widely cross-system compatible options were selected to simplify data synchronisation with the DT.

Static 2D imagery took the form of .png files, leveraging lossless compression for improved visual quality compared to JPG exports. Output of this form (Figure 2a) included: spatial profile projections (including Fol maps); subsurface radargram⁶ transects and overlays of recovered Fol spatial profiles on satellite imagery of the relevant survey environment. This extended to images showing the distribution of radar signal intensity across the survey volume⁷ at given depths, termed ‘depth slices’. Stitching together slices at regular, monotonically increasing depths generated ‘slice’ animations (Figure 2b), while interactive panning about 3D DXF object files showing generated Fol spatial profiles (Figure 3c) facilitated generation of ‘orbital’ animations. All animations took the form of MP4 (MPEG-4 Part 14) video files, which similarly provided the most practical balance between quality and compression compared to AVI, WMV and MOV formats.

Where additional relevant information was associated with output files (e.g., scan grid identifiers, date/time stamps, Fol location estimates), details were included in complementary plain text documents (Figure 2d). The use of lightweight TXT /HTML files, instead of more cumbersome DOCX or CSV formats, minimised file sizes with the intention of maximising the usability of these files, such as if key data required extraction for display on the DT interface, or if future iterations of the SIR data management subsystem required visuals to be updated.

Separate metadata files provided details on both the lock undergoing survey, and the specific volume visual output pertained to, while summary files provided an overview of each survey volume surveyed. To further streamline files, unnecessary duplication of field descriptors was avoided through the inclusion of a README file, which described the contents of each field in detail. Condensed, tabulated versions of the README are included below for: lock metadata (Table 2); volume metadata (Table 3); and volume summary (Table 4) files, respectively. A legend summarising unit and data type shorthands is also provided (Table 5).

Table 2: Breakdown of a lock metadata file

Line ID	Field Name	Unit	Data Type	Description
01	Structure ID	[/]	(s)	The lock’s unique identification code.
02	Datum Global East	[m]	(f)	UTM ⁸ easting coordinate of lock centre.
03	Datum Global North	[m]	(f)	UTM northing coordinate of lock centre.
04	Datum Global Zone	[/]	(/)	UTM zone of lock centre.
05	Date Survey Start	[/]	(s)	Starting date of survey period.
06	Reference Lock Corner	[/]	(s)	Corner referenced in metadata offset fields.

⁶ Conventional 2D radar output - subsurface cross-sections showing hyperbolic Fol artefacts.

⁷ 3D region of space inspected during an SIR scan, for a quadrant or surrounding area, that extends outward deep into the subsurface in the region of space directly behind the contact surface.

⁸ Universal Transverse Mercator – Standard coordinate system used for mapping and geolocation.

Table 3: Breakdown of a volume metadata file

Line ID	Field Name	Unit	Data Type	Description
01	Scan ID	[/]	(s)	A scan's unique identification code.
02	Local Origin East	[m]	(f)	UTM easting coordinate of scan grid origin.
03	Local Origin North	[m]	(f)	UTM northing coordinate of scan grid origin.
04	Local Origin Zone	[/]	(s)	UTM zone of scan grid origin.
05	Local Origin Height	[m]	(f)	Vertical offset between origin and lock top.
06	Local Origin Offset 0	[m]	(f)	Longitudinal ⁹ distance: lock corner to origin.
07	Local Origin Offset 1	[m]	(f)	Transverse ¹⁰ distance: lock corner to origin.
08	Number of Rows	[1]	(u)	Number of rows in grid scan pattern.
09	Number of Columns	[1]	(u)	Number of columns in grid scan pattern.
10	Transect Separation 0	[m]	(f)	Distance between successive scan rows.
11	Transect Separation 1	[m]	(f)	Distance between successive scan columns.
12	Transect Separation 2	[m]	(f)	Length of transect rows from end to end.
13	Transect Separation 3	[m]	(f)	Length of transect columns from end to end.
14	Samples Per Trace	[1]	(u)	Number of samples per radar trace recording.

Table 4: Breakdown of a volume summary file

Line ID	Field Name	Unit	Data Type	Description
01	Structure ID	[/]	(s)	The lock's unique identification code.
02	Scan ID	[/]	(s)	A scan's unique identification code.
03	Scan Start Stamp	[/]	(s)	Date and time scan began.
04	Estimated Criticality	[/]	(s)	Label indicating follow-up priority.
05	Total FoI Volume	[m ³]	(f)	Cumulative volume estimate of all Fols.
06	Blank	[/]	(/)	Blank line left as FoI separation marker.
07	FoI Summary	[1 m m]	(u f f)	Table of FoI [ID Depth Location]
...				

Table 5: Shorthands adopted for data type and unit entries in Tables {t01}-{t03}

Unit	Description	Data Type	Description
[1]	Dimensionless quantity.	(u)	Unsigned integer value.
[m]	Metres.	(f)	Float value.

⁹ Longitudinal: Direction parallel with the lock long side, advancing away from reference corner.

¹⁰ Transverse: Direction perpendicular to longitudinal, advancing away from reference corner.

[m3]	Cubic metres.	(s)	String.
[s]	Seconds.	(/)	Not applicable.
[/]	Not applicable.	...	Further entries follow.

2.2. Data Analytics

Following onsite data collection, SIR measurement files were subjected to a multi-stage analytical workflow conducted offsite. This process is divided into **three key stages**:

- (i) **Pre-processing** - is carried out at the file system level, and focuses on data format conversion, file cleaning, and enrichment.
- (ii) **Processing** - involves spatial alignment and filtering of individual transects, followed by the merging of data volumes. These are then analysed to reconstruct the 3D spatial profiles of suspected Fols.
- (iii) **Output Visualisation** - a range of output media files are generated to communicate the results effectively for both digital and physical survey reporting.

The workflow is designed to extract and clearly present estimated 3D spatial profiles of subsurface structural anomalies (Fols) associated with void formation and other indicators of structural degradation. It should be noted that all raw measurement files are preserved, and that this workflow was applied to duplicated files, enabling rollback if required at any stage.

2.2.1. Data Conversion, Cleaning and Enrichment

Pre-processing begins with data merging and archiving operations. Any physical records associated with the SIR survey are digitised and catalogued within a dedicated directory, as defined in Deliverable 2.2. These records typically include handwritten notes from SIR operatives, which provide concise summaries of key transect file identifiers, highlighting dataset transitions, along with brief descriptions of trajectory directions or anomalies (e.g., local obstructions) to contextualise the measurement data and guide transect-specific actions (e.g., truncation of overspill).

Digitisation and conversion processes are performed manually and informed through consultation between the practitioners who conducted the survey. Once verified, records for both lock wall quadrants and surrounding area scans are formalised into a series of digital spreadsheets (Figure 3) to support efficient navigation and integration throughout subsequent processing stages. Although no files are deleted during the subsequent cleaning process, those marked for omission are excluded from all further stages of analysis. Files may be omitted for various reasons, including corruption during data capture or transfer. Most commonly, omission resulted from premature scan termination caused by operator error, in which case the measurement was immediately repeated and stored in a new file, rendering the original file redundant.

The calculation and application of antenna heading offsets are presented below. Due to physical constraints of the SIR system's frame and pushcart configurations, it is not possible to mount the GNSS measurement antenna directly above the midpoint of the radar antenna footprint. Therefore, the offset between the antenna midpoints must be incorporated into the positioning data to ensure maximum accuracy.

(a)					(b)						
Scanned Volume	Relevant Transect ID(s)	Direction of Antenna Advance	Usable File? [Y/N]	Further Note(s)	Scanned Quadrant/Area	Relevant Transect ID(s)	Direction of Antenna Advance	Usable File? [Y/N]	Other Relevant Images/File(s)	Further Note(s)	
20241202	Q2	0931	HB	Y	Day 2 09:35						
20241202	Q2	0932	HS	N	Discard file - measurement repeated						
20241202	Q2	0933	HS	Y	Q2 vertical increments between rows 33cm "Close" W!	20241204	AA	0318	TO	Y	PULSE DELAY 278 Columns(TD AT) 512 Samples. Range 900m 7.5m (File 0318.SGY is 2.4MB vs 1.1.5 of others!)
20241202	Q2	0934	HB	Y		20241204	AA	0319	TI	Y	
20241202	Q2	0935	HS	Y	Zoned 96%	20241204	AA	0320	TO	Y	514L
20241202	Q2	0936	HB	Y		20241204	AA	0321	TI	Y	(1.13MB)
20241202	Q2	0937	HS	Y		20241204	AA	0322	TO	Y	(1.44MB)
20241202	Q2	0938	HB	N	Discard file - measurement repeated	20241204	AA	0323	TI	Y	HR VICE(J) (1.02MB)
20241202	Q2	0939	HB	Y		20241204	AA	0324	TO	Y	(1.48MB)
20241202	Q2	0940	HS	Y		20241204	AA	0325	TI	Y	HR PHOTOS(1.13MB)
20241202	Q2	0941	HB	N	Discard file - measurement repeated	20241204	AA	0326	TI	N	51099C
20241202	Q2	0942	HB	Y		20241204	AA	0327	TO	Y	(1.20MB)
20241202	Q2	0943	HS	N	Discard file - measurement repeated	20241204	AA	0328	TI	Y	(1.04MB)
20241202	Q2	0944	HS	Y		20241204	AA	0329	TO	Y	
20241202	Q2	0945	HB	Y		20241204	AA	0330	TI	Y	(Area 4 direction of longitudinal offset between columns (C) connects (339-338) as 18 (distance 999))
20241202	Q2	0946	HS	N	Discard file - measurement repeated						
20241202	Q2	0947	HS	N							
20241202	Q2	0948	HS	Y	11.3 MB (slightly underweight) ?						
20241202	Q2	0949	HB	Y							
20241202	Q2	0950	HS	N	Discard file - measurement repeated	20241204	AA	0331	TO	Y	
20241202	Q2	0951	HS	Y		20241204	AA	0332	TI	Y	
20241202	Q2	0952	HB	N	Discard file - measurement repeated	20241204	AA	0333	TO	Y	
20241202	Q2	0953	HB	Y		20241204	AA	0334	TI	Y	
20241202	Q2	0954	HS	N	Discard file - measurement repeated	20241204	AA	0335	TO	Y	(Discard file appears valid, notes indicate incorrect file was reported in file 0336.SGY) "Repeat"
20241202	Q2	0955	HS	Y							
20241202	Q2	0956	HB	Y	Surface Hole						
20241202	Q2	0957	HS	N	Discard File						

Figure 3: Digitised SIR survey logs for a survey quadrant (a), and surrounding area scan (b)

For the frame configuration (Figure 4a), the GNSS antenna is offset by 0.185m longitudinally and 0.980m vertically from the local origin of the frame, over which the antenna midpoint is positioned at the home location at the start of a quadrant scan. Since all positional measurements for the frame are made relative to this local coordinate system, only a heading offset correction to the local origin is required.

For the pushcart configuration (Figure 4b), the process is more complex. The front and rear wheel contact points serve as reference points for the start and end of scan trajectories. The radar antenna is offset from the cart centre to allow clamping to a rigid surface, preventing drift during movement, while the GNSS antenna is clamped to the cart handle, located at the zero marker in the diagram. Heading offsets along each transect were calculated based on the relative separation between the antenna midpoint and each wheel centre, measured physically using a tape prior to the survey. In practice, a heading offset of 0.54 m was applied.

Figure 4: Antenna heading offsets for SIR scan quadrants (a) and areas (b)

The next stage of pre-processing is bad block and empty trace removal.

A ‘bad block’ refers to a section of a recorded radargram displaying a significant discontinuity unrelated to the physical survey environment. The most common example is a vertical offset between the direct arrival wavefront and the 0m depth marker, typically appearing as a solid black bar (Figure 5a). This issue was traced to a recurring buffer overflow bug in the Prism2

measurement software, outside the control of the SIR development team. As this type of bad block caused a uniform vertical to offset across the dataset, recovery was achieved by applying a time-cutting method (Figure 5b), which removed the anomalous region and realigned the direct arrival wavefront with the 0m depth marker.

Figure 5: Transect ‘bad blocks’ (a) suppressed via time cutting (b); empty trace removal (c)

An ‘empty trace’ (Figure 5c) refers to a section of the radargram corresponding to a stationary antenna. It is characterised by a smeared appearance, where amplitude variations within individual traces are effectively duplicated across the lateral axis over a finite interval. These instances were flagged in the digitised records and occurred almost exclusively during pushcart operation, typically when the cart encountered a ground undulation that temporarily halted movement and required additional force to overcome. As with time-cutting, these regions were trimmed in Prism2 to remove empty trace artefacts.

The final stage of pre-processing was ‘trace stacking’, a form of transect file compression. This step was essential to improve file handling efficiency and enable synchronisation with the software platform used in subsequent workflow stages. Each working directory instance was limited to a maximum capacity of 500MB, necessitating compression to avoid system resource saturation during the generation of 3D visual outputs.

Raw transects were recorded at a sampling rate of approximately 3,800 traces per metre, with 255 samples per trace. Stacking compressed only the lateral axis through windowed averaging, whereby the dataset is partitioned into sequential intervals of N traces—denoted the applied ‘compression factor’, defined as a power of 2. Each interval was replaced with a mean trace, computed by averaging the amplitude at each sample point across the N traces (Figure 6a).

Figure 6: Transect stacking procedure (a) implemented in Prism2 (b).

In this study, a compression factor of $N = 8$ was applied using Prism2, independently to five transects at a time for every transect within each survey volume. This reduced individual transects file sizes from approximately 12MB at around 17,000 traces, to 1.5MB or just over 2,000 traces (Figure 6b). The resulting raw data directory sizes were approximately 100MB for quadrant scans, and between 100–200MB for surrounding areas. The higher variability in the latter was due to the greater spatial variation in survey grid extent associated with pushcart operation, which, unlike quadrant scans, were not physically constrained by the frame dimensions and could achieved greater maximal antenna displacements from the local origin.

2.2.2. Spatial Alignment of Measurements

The processing stage begins with the spatial alignment of transects in three-dimensional space. This step integrates the individual 2D datasets into a single 3D data volume for each survey area. Transect positioning follows the same serpentine scan pattern used during data acquisition, with each transect aligned parallel to its scan trajectory, oriented such as to extend outward into the subsurface media, such that the 0m depth marker intersects the contact surface (Figure 7). Transects intersect orthogonally at points where scan trajectories cross, as illustrated by the red and blue lines in the diagram. It should be noted that, due to the physical footprint of the antenna head and the carriage mechanism on which it travels, scan trajectories terminate short of the outermost boundaries of the survey area. Additionally, to account for the alternating direction of travel during data collection, every second transect is reversed along its respective travel axis.

The diagram indicates the local origin of the survey volume with a white circle containing a black cross, from which coloured axis lines extend. The red line represents the lateral longitudinal x-axis, aligned parallel to the long edge of the lock. The blue line denotes the z-axis, defined as

perpendicular to the x-axis within the plane of the contact surface—depicted in transparent grey—over which the antenna travels. The y-axis corresponds to displacement into the subsurface, with the contact surface located at the 0m marker. By definition, the y-axis is always orthogonal to the contact surface plane. It is important to note that the orientation of this plane varies depending on the survey context: it may be vertical (for wall quadrant scans) or horizontal (for pushcart scans across areas adjacent to the lock). For consistency and improved clarity in visualising subsurface Fols, survey volume outputs will, where possible, be displayed with the contact surface horizontally aligned at the top of the volume and increasing subsurface depth scanned into the subsurface extending downward.

Figure 7: Transect alignment in 3D relative to individual scan trajectories (arrows)

Once aligned within the local coordinate system of the survey volume, the local origin is mapped to its corresponding georeferenced position in the WGS84 UTM model. This transformation enables all other data points within the volume to be georeferenced accordingly. Satellite imagery of the surrounding area can be overlaid onto the contact surface of the resulting volume, providing spatial context for the survey location. The precise georeferenced coordinates of the local origin are determined through a combination of GNSS data acquired by the positioning antenna (mounted on the frame and pushcart, respectively) through the Prism2 geolocation interface tables and physical measurements of distance between the frame centre and identifiable landmarks visible in satellite imagery such as CCTV poles, mooring posts, and the intersections between grass and concrete around the lock's area.

2.2.3. Profile Filtering

Processing moves on to the application of a series of filtering techniques to the data volume, executed in a defined sequence. These techniques progress from microscale enhancements—applied at the level of individual transects to macroscale enhancements that consider the full data volume.

The process begins with the estimation of the dielectric model, informed by a combination of survey records, predefined mappings for common survey media embedded within the software, and operator expertise. In environments characterised by complex subsurface stratigraphy, a multilayer model is employed, allowing the dielectric constant to vary with depth and lateral displacement from the local origin. In more homogeneous settings, such as concrete lock walls or moderately wet earth, a simplified single-layer model is sufficient. For these media, typical

dielectric constant values are 6 (corresponding to a radar signal propagation velocity of 0.122 m/ns) for concrete, and 21.3 (0.065 m/ns) for earth.

Time-zero correction is then applied to align the first positive peak of the direct arrival wavefront in each radar trace with the 0m depth marker. This step ensures consistent alignment of all transects at the contact surface, preserving the spatial coherence of subsurface profiles and reducing the risk of distortion—particularly the misalignment of hyperbolae representing the same suspected Fol across intersecting transects. The correction is performed using a combination of automated edge detection and manual adjustment of the time-zero parameter, guided by operator judgement. This is the case for almost all processing steps discussed from this point onward, though will not be explicitly stated hereafter for brevity.

Gain compensation is then applied in two stages. Initially, all transects undergo a uniform gain increase of 10–15 dB, amplifying the radar signal consistently across both the lateral and depth axes to enhance the contrast of potential Fols against the background noise. A secondary, manually defined gain is then applied using a parameterised piecewise function along the depth axis. This function progressively increases gain from 0dB to 30dB with increasing depth, compensating for the natural attenuation of signal strength at greater depths. This approach enhances the visibility of weaker reflection events caused by longer propagation paths and increased scattering in deeper subsurface regions.

Denosing through Band Pass Filtering (BPF) is then applied (see Figure 8). At a fundamental level, radar signal 'noise' refers to any unwanted, non-informative energy—irrespective of frequency—that obscures features associated with the true subsurface structure, thereby reducing interpretive clarity. This noise becomes increasingly dominant with depth, as the radar signal attenuates¹¹. Noise sources can be broadly categorised as background noise—arising from natural fine-scale heterogeneity within the subsurface, antenna–surface coupling artefacts, and electromagnetic interference (EMI)—or instrument-related noise, originating from internal signal reflections and electronic components. BPF is used to suppress frequency components outside a user-defined bandwidth, typically centred around the antenna's operating frequency and spanning approximately $\pm 50\%$ of that value. In the SIR system, high-frequency noise dominates, particularly from microscale subsurface heterogeneity and the extended transmission line connecting the antenna to the main electronics enclosure. As such, the BPF is configured to rapidly attenuate signal components above 1.5GHz.

An additional noise reduction step is background suppression, applied at two levels. For individual transects, background subtraction involves calculating the average trace response across the entire transect and subtracting this from each trace. This process helps to suppress unwanted horizontal line artefacts, often caused by ringing¹² effects near hyperbolic reflections associated with near-surface interfaces of hollow Fols, primarily voids. At the level of the full, merged data volume, a similar approach is employed by computing the mean trace across all transects within the survey volume and subtracting it from each trace. This volume-wide background subtraction effectively reduces large-scale, consistent artefacts such as antenna

¹¹ The maximum penetration depth of a transect is defined as the point at which the radar signal becomes indistinguishable from background noise. As this threshold is best identified through visual assessment, it is often more efficient for operatives to estimate it manually.

¹² Ringing phenomena are repeated oscillations in the GPR signal caused by multiple internal reflections between closely spaced material boundaries with different electrical properties (e.g., the walls of a hollow buried pipe).

coupling effects and persistent environmental noise patterns that remain constant across multiple transects—artefacts that may not be fully addressed by individual transect subtraction, as they can manifest as subtle but coherent signals throughout the entire dataset.

Figure 8: Output from processing techniques applied to SIR datasets: (a) BPF; (b) Gain Compensation; (c) FK-Migration and (d) Hilbert Transform

The final stages of processing involve converting hyperbolic artefacts associated with Fols into more accurate representations of the physical subsurface geometry. These hyperbolae arise from the conical propagation pattern of the radar signal emitted by the antenna, which detects the presence of Fols both before and after the antenna passes directly overhead. Frequency-wavenumber (FK) migration is applied to the 3D data volume to collapse these hyperbolic artefacts into point reflectors, thereby improving the localisation of near-surface interfaces associated with suspected Fols. This is complemented by Hilbert transform processing, which computes the signal envelope to emphasise localised regions of consistent reflection strength and continuity, aiding in the delineation of boundary interfaces. Together, these techniques enhance the clarity of Fols within the data volume and improve the reconstruction of the 3D spatial profile.

2.2.4. 3D Spatial Profile Recovery

Output visualisation focuses on the extraction and rendering of 3D spatial profiles associated with suspected Fols within each survey data volume. To facilitate this, the combined data volume undergoes depth slicing (hereafter referred to as ‘slicing’). This process begins with interpolation to increase the data resolution by a factor of three, thereby enhancing spatial continuity. Subsequently, a series of two-dimensional plots of normalised radar signal amplitude are generated across the full lateral extent of the contact surface footprint. Each slice corresponds to

a distinct depth layer within the data volume, spaced at uniform intervals of 0.025m. The resulting plots resemble heatmaps, with higher-intensity radar responses shown in red and lower-intensity background responses in blue (Figure 9a).

Figure 9: Analysis of 2D slices (a) highlights Fols (red) and informs their 3D profiles (b)

At a more technical level, slices are generated using the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) method, a form of weighted interpolation in which the influence of neighbouring sample points on a query point decreases with distance. This influence follows a reciprocal relationship, typically of the form $1/d^p$, where d denotes the distance between the query point and a neighbouring sample point, and p is a power parameter that controls the rate of decay. Border clipping is applied at the edges of the slice footprints to blank output in these regions. This is necessary because near the boundaries, the interpolation search radius can extend beyond the measured domain, so clipping is used to mitigate the risk of generating false artefacts that can obscure or degrade the visibility of genuine Fols within the dataset.

Three-dimensional isosurfaces are generated to match the spatial profiles observed in the image slices. By cycling through sequential slices and viewing them as video frames, an experienced operator can visually interpret the 3D spatial characteristics of suspected Fols, as each slice represents a cross-sectional estimate at a specific depth. The operator selects a threshold parameter for isosurface generation—ranging from 0 to 1—corresponding to the normalised radar signal amplitude at the outer boundary of the Fols. This process is inherently subjective, as physical boundaries are typically gradual rather than perfectly discontinuous.

An iterative bisection method is employed to enable a repeatable and systematic approach to threshold selection. The process begins with an initial threshold $I_0 = 0.5$, the midpoint of the normalised amplitude range. If the resulting isosurface appears sparse relative to the geometry suggested by the slices, the threshold is increased to $I_1 = 0.75$. Conversely, if the isosurface exhibits overfitting - referred to as domain saturation¹³ - the threshold is reduced to $I_1 = 0.25$. This bisection procedure continues iteratively (Figure 10), following the relation:

$$I_{n+1} = \frac{I_n + I_{n-1}}{2}$$

¹³ This is characterised by the generation of numerous small isosurfaces distributed across the entire domain, with no localised region exhibiting a significantly higher density of structures. As I is increased further, such isosurfaces eventually coalesce into large, slab-like forms that span the full lateral extent of the domain.

where $n > 1$ denotes the current iteration index. The process terminates when $100I_{n+1}$ no longer yields an integer value. In practice, selected isovalues typically fall within the range 0.6–0.8. A final value below this range suggests that the applied constant gain is too low and should be increased accordingly; conversely, a value above this range indicates excessive gain. This check does not fundamentally affect the shape or structure of the recovered isosurfaces, but serves as a consistency control measure within the processing workflow.

Figure 10: Iterative bisection method for isosurface threshold parameter selection

2.3. Feature Analysis

The isosurfaces generated during 3D spatial profile recovery represent the combined spatial profiles of all Fols detected within a subsurface volume. This composite representation requires further segmentation to isolate and distinguish individual¹⁴ Fols. The process comprises two stages. First, each suspected Fol is formally identified and characterised, with spatial footprints estimated and, where possible, inferences made regarding its form and composition. Second, the Fol's position within the local coordinate system must be determined, documented, and communicated to end-users, accompanied by relevant metrics indicating its criticality to support assessment of significance and prioritisation of follow-up actions for maintenance crews.

2.3.1. Identification and Characterisation

Fol identification is conducted by an experienced radar technician through visual inspection of isometric spatial profile projections, supported by interactive orbital views provided by the data processing software (see Section 2.5). This method was deemed the most practical, as implementing a bespoke segmentation framework based on topologically aware deep learning models (Tong, Z. et al., 2020; Zhou, Y. et al., 2024) or convolutional neural network architectures (Mizutani T. et al., 2024; Wang, D. et al., 2025) lay beyond the feasible scope of SIR development within the project's timescale. Nevertheless, such approaches represent a viable direction for future enhancement of this technology.

For each survey volume, bounding boxes¹⁵ were delineated on 2D planar projections of the surface geometry, viewed in the plane of the contact surface, to mark the perceived maximum spatial extent of each Fol identified within the volume. The resulting overlaid graphic was

¹⁴ A single, genuine subsurface defect may manifest in an SIR scan as multiple smaller 3D structures, which should be collectively identified and flagged as a single Fol.

¹⁵ It should be noted that, although represented as 2D boxes in the Fol Map (a 2D projection), these are in fact the projections of cuboidal bounding volumes that enclose the corresponding 3D isosurfaces.

designated the 'Fol Map' for that survey volume. Each Fol was assigned a unique integer index to facilitate efficient referencing, in keeping with the indexing convention adopted for each survey volume and asset under inspection (see Deliverable D5.2). Indices were assigned sequentially in the order of Fol identification. Where no significant¹⁶ Fols were detected within a volume, the Fol Map was explicitly labelled 'No Fol Identified'.

Although inherently subjective, several indicative criteria can assist in distinguishing one Fol from its adjacent neighbours. These include*, but are not limited to:

- **Isolated profiles** with no immediate neighbouring isosurfaces, suggesting a highly localised structural anomaly.
- **Lack of geometric conformity**, where the faces of neighbouring isosurfaces do not exhibit shared curvature or parallelism, reducing the likelihood of them forming part of the same physical structure.
- **Intervening fine-scale isosurfaces** located between two or more substantially larger neighbouring isosurfaces, potentially indicating a single larger profile fragmented by partial occlusion due to environmental clutter or an overly aggressive threshold selection.
- **Threshold persistence**, where multiple adjacent isosurfaces remain distinct across varying isosurface thresholds but merge at values below approximately $I = 0.8$ suggesting they may represent a single physical Fol.

(*) It should be emphasised that each assessment is context-dependent; satisfying any combination of these criteria does not guarantee that a given Fol is not part of a larger or smaller subsurface anomaly, or that the observed profile is an exact likeness of its physical counterpart.

Similarly, once identified, the spatial profiles of these isosurfaces can provide insight into the potential shape, form, and composition of the subsurface anomaly. As previously noted, these indicators are not definitive, but examples include:

- **Absence of deeper structures** – where an isosurface lies close to the contact surface and the underlying region contains no Fols (including fine-scale isosurfaces), this may indicate either increased moisture content, which attenuates radar signals more rapidly than surrounding material, and/or the presence of a strong reflective medium, such as metal, which as a perfect electrical conductor largely blocks radar transmission.
- **Non-uniformity and asymmetry** – often characteristic of naturally occurring anomalies (e.g., voids), in contrast to man-made structures (e.g., concrete block joints, drainage channels) that typically display sharper, more uniform, and self-similar surfaces.
- **Fragmentation at footprint extremities** – where a single large isosurface appears broken into multiple smaller isosurfaces, potentially indicating active growth of the anomaly.
- **Thickened profiles** – as data processing does not directly suppress ring-down artefacts, hollow subsurface structures may appear with artificially thickened depth profiles relative to surrounding Fols, serving as an indicator of potential void presence.
- **Smooth, geometric surfaces** – spherical, cylindrical, or arched top surfaces are more closely associated with layer separation events or void formations, which are self-supporting under surrounding load. In contrast, solid inclusions (e.g., rocks, rubble, debris) tend to exhibit greater spatial variation, naturally displacing surrounding material.

¹⁶ In practice, it is neither feasible nor sufficiently accurate to designate every individual isosurface as an Fol. For the purposes of this work, Fols are defined as anomalies of sufficient scale to constitute a noteworthy finding. Within the context of this survey, this corresponds to anomalies with dominant length scales which exceeded approximately 100 mm.

- **Isotopically flat upper surfaces** – consistent depth across the upper surface of an FoI may indicate void or cavity formation through washout or collapse, where progressive delamination of poorly bonded material reduces depth variation over time.

Following this process, key metadata for each identified FoI is compiled into an accompanying ASCII text file, suffixed ‘_summary.txt’. This file includes the unique asset identifier, volume identifier, and the date–time stamp corresponding to the start of the volume scan. It also contains a table of local position coordinates for the centre point of each FoI bounding box, enabling end-users to precisely locate each suspected FoI within the local coordinate grid—information essential for planning and executing any subsequent targeted maintenance activities.

2.3.2. Criticality Estimation

For practical application of SIR findings to support infrastructure asset resilience, a definable and quantifiable measure of ‘criticality’ was established to flag where urgent follow-up action may be required (e.g., immediate intervention, planned maintenance, or no further action for findings of negligible concern). The criticality estimate for each SIR volume is recorded in the metadata file suffixed “_summary.txt”, located alongside the processed output data for each survey volume.

This estimate comprises two components:

1. A quantitative metric (in cubic metres) representing the total volume occupied by suspected Fols within the survey volume. Lower values are indicative of fewer significant Fols and, by implication, a healthier structural condition.
2. A categorical label - ‘HIGH’, ‘MEDIUM’, ‘LOW’, or ‘NONE’—assigned by the analysing radar technician to provide an at-a-glance indication of criticality. A ‘HIGH’ designation denotes a volume warranting urgent follow-up, for example, this may be a situation where a high number of Fols are detected in a single volume, an FoI is located in a critical area within a volume, or a rapidly expanding footprint is observed in a volume when examined across multiple chronologically ordered surveys.

As with FoI characterisation, criticality estimation is inherently multifactorial and relies on expert judgement. These labels enable the digital twin (DT) to expedite dissemination of survey results and assist end-users in filtering out healthy volumes, thereby directing focus and resources towards areas of greatest significance for continued asset integrity.

2.4. Quality Assurance of Tools Used for SIR Visualisation

As a multistage process, data analytics for SIR surveys is inherently complex, drawing on established GPR best practices (Baker, G.S., Jordan, T.E., and Pardy, J., 2007), (Oldenburg, D. et al., 2017), (Daniels, J.J., 2000). A key challenge lies in quality assurance, given the inherent difficulty in ascertaining the true nature of surveyed subsurface geometry. Traditional invasive validation techniques, such as exploratory boreholes coupled with endoscopic visual probes, can provide direct confirmation, but risk compromising the integrity of otherwise healthy structural assets. This was therefore not a viable option for examination of the in-service structural assets. SIR survey work was focused on in this project.

To address this, a non-invasive validation strategy was adopted using numerically simulated datasets generated via the open-source EM-wave simulation toolkit gprMax (Warren, C. et al., 2016), based on Maxwell’s equations, to produce simulated transect measurements across a 3D survey volume containing known target geometries. These simulations were processed using GPRPy (Plattner, A.M., 2020) for data cleaning and preparation. Further technical details on the

setup and implementation of similar numerical simulation workflows are presented in McDonald, T. et al. (2025).

With complete knowledge of the ground-truth subsurface geometry available as a baseline, simulated transect data were processed through the geotechnical software and the resulting 3D spatial profiles compared directly against their known forms. Example target configurations embedded in the simulated volumes included, but were not limited to: (i) a single metallic sphere offset from the central depth axis; (ii) two overlapping but non-intersecting hollow cylindrical pipes; and (iii) three cubes of decreasing size and identical material aligned linearly.

This work demonstrated that subsurface anomalies were consistently detectable using the data analytics workflow, with targets exceeding the established 100mm dominant length-scale threshold for anomaly intervention (agreed between UNEW, VNF, and industry practitioners; see Deliverable D2.3) reliably distinguished from the background medium, even in the presence of heterogeneous noise from environmental clutter. Furthermore, the simulations informed several of the Fol segmentation hallmarks listed in Section 2.3.1 - most notably, the influence of ringing phenomena on apparent isosurface thickness in case (ii). This work also directly contributed to refining the isosurface threshold-selection method, leading to the adoption of the iterative bisection approach described in Section 2.2.4.

Quality assurance testing was extended to include physical measurement data, acquired using the same 1GHz shielded antenna and radar controller hardware later integrated into the final SIR system design. Following the procedure described in McDonald, T. et al. (2025), a wooden container of approximately 0.5m³ was constructed and filled with sand to replicate a homogeneous subsurface survey volume. Metallic spheres of 100mm, 60mm, and 30mm diameter were embedded to simulate structural anomalies. A grid of transect trajectories was recorded by manually advancing the antenna across the full contact surface area. The data were processed using the SIR geotechnical software. Results corroborated simulation (iii), with the 100mm and 60mm targets successfully detected and their three-dimensional spatial profiles accurately resolved.

Following data collection from the river pilot test (see Section 3), an additional quality assurance assessment was conducted on practical survey data from the inspection of a real lock wall quadrant (Q002-1[^]) and the surrounding area scan (A004-0#). To evaluate potential gains in data collection efficiency, this test examined the effect of adopting a bidirectional scan grid pattern (two perpendicular axes) on the resulting 3D spatial profiles of identified Fols, compared with those obtained from a unidirectional scan pattern comprised from subsets of transects along each axis independently. If bidirectionality was found to yield negligible differences, the analytical process would have been adapted to use only the unidirectional transect subset for each survey volume, enabling future surveys to capture data along a single axis and thereby improve data collection efficiency.

For each dataset, slices spanning the full depth of the volume were superimposed to produce a 'stacked slice' representation, displaying the relative footprints of all Fols within a single 2D visual (see Section 2.5). Additionally, all isosurfaces were projected from an isometric viewing angle to further aid interpretive clarity¹⁷.

¹⁷ As throughout this work, detailed analysis also employed the interactive display functionality of the SIR geometric software, enabling each volume to be freely rotated and scaled to enhance the clarity of identified Fols.

For the lock wall quadrant, subsurface visuals from slicing (Figure 11) showed that longitudinal-only transects produced results comparable to those from the full bidirectional grid. In contrast, transverse-only transects, while detecting Fols in the lower corners and upper section, failed to resolve the extent of the upper-section Fol as clearly.

Figure 11: Comparison of 2D stacked slices for Q002-1, recovered using: (a) longitudinal transects only; (b) transverse transects only; (c) full area scan grid.

Isosurface renders (Figure 12) revealed more pronounced differences: the transverse-only grid did not identify any significant Fol profiles, while the longitudinal-only grid exhibited signs of domain saturation, obscuring the vast majority of localised subsurface structures present. In comparison, the bidirectional grid output clearly resolved four distinct anomalies.

Figure 12: Comparison of 3D isosurfaces for Q002-1, recovered using: (a) longitudinal transects only; (b) transverse transects only; (c) full area scan grid

Comparable results were obtained from the surrounding-area scan, although deviations between recovered spatial profiles were less pronounced, reflecting the more fragmented distribution of subsurface Fols within the examined volume. In the slice data output (Figure 13), both the bidirectional and transverse-only grids detected the strong reflector in the upper-right corner—absent in the longitudinal-only output—along with the majority of weaker reflection events (green) near the left boundary. In both unidirectional slice outputs, lines of reduced reflection amplitude (blue) aligned with the trajectories of sequential transect measurements. These were attributed

to interpolation artefacts caused by the markedly reduced measurement density along the complementary axis of the unidirectional datasets.

Figure 13: Comparison of 2D stacked slices for A004-0, recovered using: (a) longitudinal transects only; (b) transverse transects only; (c) full area scan grid

Isosurface renders (Figure 14) showed slightly greater consistency than those for the lock wall volumes; however, Fol footprints were markedly exaggerated over both lateral axes in the unidirectional setting, particularly in the central region of the transverse-only grid.

Figure 14: Comparison of 3D isosurfaces for A004-0, recovered using: (a) longitudinal transects only; (b) transverse transects only; (c) full area scan grid

Collectively, these findings supported the adoption of bidirectional scan patterns for both data analytics and all subsequent practical surveys. It was evident from this work that incorporating radar response data from transects acquired along both lateral axes, would deliver a more comprehensive and consistently accurate recovery of Fol spatial profiles than a unidirectional approach.

2.5. Generation of Multimedia Output Files

The final stage of SIR data analysis involves generating visual outputs in multimedia file formats. To maximise clarity, multiple output types are produced, as outlined in Deliverable D5.2. A

breakdown is presented in Table 6. For brevity, the terms in the second column for Quadrant and Area are denoted 'Q' and 'A' respectively.

Generated multimedia files are collectively referred to as SIR 'processed data'. These are stored in a directory of the same name, whose parent directory is indexed by the unique identifier of the corresponding volume. Within the SIR data hierarchy, processed data storage is organised over two levels. At the top level, multimedia files relating to the entire volume are located. A subdirectory (2D_Frames) contains the individual frames used to generate the slice animation file. Additional subdirectories are created for each identified Fol, containing the corresponding transect intersection and depth slice imagery, as indicated by (*) in Table 6.

Table 6: Summary of multimedia output file types

Name	Application	Format	Description
Multislice	All	PNG (2D)	Uses colour hue and intensity to convey depth, prevalence, and extent of Fols.
Multislice + Iso.	All	PNG (2D)	As above, with isosurfaces overlaid.
Projection (ISO)	All	PNG (2D)	Composite image of all isosurfaces in a volume from an isometric viewing angle.
Projection (XY)	All	PNG (2D)	As above, viewed in the XY plane.
Projection (XZ)	All	PNG (2D)	As above, viewed in the XZ plane.
Projection (YZ)	All	PNG (2D)	As above, viewed in the YZ plane.
Satellite	Q	PNG (2D)	Overlay of the contact surface area of a volume on a satellite map of the survey location.
Satellite + Iso. (NW)	A	PNG (2D)	As above, viewed from the north-west aspect, with isosurfaces overlaid.
Satellite + Iso. (SE)	A	PNG (2D)	As above, viewed from the south-east aspect.
Slice	All	PNG (2D)	Frame(s) from an animation of a depth slice, showing Fol footprints.
Slices (All)	All	MP4 (2.5D**)	Animation cycling through slice frames in order of increasing depth.
Slices (All) (Stacked)	All	PNG (2D)	Superposition of all slices across the full volume, showing all Fol footprints.
Object	All	DXF (3D)	Interactive 3D representation of all isosurfaces in a given volume.
Orbital	All	MP4 (2.5D**)	Video rotating the view around all isosurfaces in a given volume.
Orbital (Raw)	All	MP4 (2.5D**)	Original orbital animation before speed adjustment, cropping, and compression.

Map	All	PNG (2D)	Map showing the locations and labels of each Fol in a given volume.
Summary	All	TXT; HTML (1D)	Metadata file containing criticality estimate, total Fol volume, and bounding box centre in the volume's local coordinate system.
Fol Iso + Transects	All*	PNG (2D)	Isosurface for each Fol, overlaid with any intersecting 3D-aligned transects.
Fol Slices (Stacked)	All*	PNG (2D)	Finite depth slice across the full depth of an Fol's bounding box.

(*) Returned providing at least one Fol is identified in a given volume.

(**) Output described as 2.5D includes animated graphics and video footage, which are 2D media but provide an enhanced sense of depth through perspective cues and sequential frame rendering, in contrast to the static isometric projection of a 3D scene into a single 2D image.

Where visual output files include a representation of the local coordinate grid, or additional visual cues are required to convey the orientation of a given volume, the local coordinate origin is marked by a white circle containing a black cross. From this point, coloured direction markers¹⁸ indicate the increasing longitudinal x-axis (red), the perpendicular y-axis (green), and the z-axis (blue). Recall that the direction extending into the subsurface is always associated with the y-axis.

The remainder of this section explores several key types of multimedia output file.

Isosurfaces generated from the data analytics workflow are viewed in the SIR geotechnical software as interactive 3D objects, which can be rotated in three-dimensional space and scaled to facilitate inspection and characterisation efforts. The spatial profiles can be exported from the software as Drawing Exchange Format (DXF) files, containing the 3D object formed from the union of all isosurfaces in a given volume, and can be rendered in a similar interactive manner using the browser-based freeware Autodesk Viewer (Figure 15a).

An orbital can be regarded as the 2.5D count counterpart of the 3D object file. As the name suggests, orbitals provide an orbital view of a full volume's isosurfaces, contextualising the relative position of each Fol with respect to its neighbours and the local coordinate origin. Such visualisations are well suited for inclusion in digital dashboards (e.g., for the DT) to summarise a volume's Fol content, offering end users an efficient means of viewing the entirety of a survey volume without manually navigating the 3D object file—an operation that can be challenging, particularly for non-specialists.

This output type is generated semi-automatically, using Autodesk Viewer to capture multiple video frames of isosurfaces within a given volume from varying view angles (Figure 15b). View angles are adjusted manually, while frame capture is automated. The recorded frames are then processed using the web-based freeware EZGIF (Figure 15c), which crops the frames, adjusts the framerate to reduce playback speed, and compiles the image sequence into an MPEG-4 (MP4) encoded video file. This file format was selected for its high levels of cross-compatibility with various display platforms.

Returned 3D spatial profiles can also be exported as 2D plane projection images in Portable Network Graphics (PNG) format. A plane projection represents the 'shadow' cast onto a face of

¹⁸ For orbitals, note that markers point opposite to the direction of the increasing coordinate.

the volume's outer bounding box by a virtual light source placed directly opposite, or equivalently, the view seen by a camera positioned at that location.

Figure 15: Orbital generation utilising free, web-based tools for 3D rendering (a), frame stitching (b), image processing and sequence encoding (c)

The 3D spatial profiles within a given volume (Figure 16a) can be rendered using either a perspective projection (Figure 16b) or an orthographic projection (Figure 16c). Perspective projection simulates depth by scaling objects inversely with their distance from the virtual camera, making distant objects appear smaller and thereby conveying scene depth and relative FoI placement. In contrast, orthographic projection preserves uniform scale and parallel lines regardless of depth, allowing accurate comparison of FoI footprints, but can make it more difficult to interpret their relative spatial positioning. For this reason, SIR employs perspective projection by default.

Plane projections are a well-established method for representing 3D scenes in 2D, and can in some cases be more effective than 3D visualisations alone, as they may better highlight subtle

variations in F_{ol} geometry (Figure 16d). The SIR geotechnical software supports projection onto the XY, XZ, and YZ planes (Figure 17), defined by the principal axes of the survey volume.

Figure 16: Illustration of subsurface geometry (a) under perspective (b) and orthographic (c) 2D projection. The choice of projection plane can produce differing geometrical representations (d)

Figure 17: Relative orientations between contact surface (light grey) and 2D projection planes (dark grey) for SIR survey volume (black) of quadrant (a-c) and surrounding area scans (d-f)

It is also possible to generate slice imagery. A slice represents a 2D cross-section of the subsurface in a plane parallel to the contact surface, visually conveying radar signal strength at each sampled point within that plane. Where measurement data is absent—typically between successive transects—values are estimated via linear interpolation, as described in Section 2.2.

Where an FoI intersects the plane, its 2D spatial footprint at that depth becomes visible. Strong reflection events, typically associated with subsurface anomalies, are indicated in red; weaker signals, often representing background material, appear in blue. Each survey volume is divided into multiple depth slices (Figure 18a), with a fixed vertical interval of 0.025m. By default, individual slices are infinitesimally thin (Figure 18b), and are exported and compiled—following a process similar to that used for orbitals—into an MP4 animation cycling through the sequential slices in order of increasing depth into the subsurface.

It is also possible to superimpose adjacent slices across a localised depth range (e.g., spanning an individual FoI), or across the full vertical extent of the survey volume (Figure 18c). This process, referred to as slice ‘stacking’, should not be confused with the similarly named transect compression method described in Section 2.2.1.

Figure 18: Illustration of ‘slicing’ a 3D survey volume (a) into a discrete number of 2D planes, either of infinitesimal thickness (b), or superimposed to produce finite thickness slices (c)

To contextualise SIR outputs, isosurfaces, slices, and transects can be overlaid onto satellite imagery of the survey environment using the MapBox provider. A satellite overlay is generated for each SIR survey volume (Figure 19a), displaying either the full-depth stacked slice (for quadrants) or the recovered 3D isosurfaces (for surrounding area scans). For surrounding areas, views from both the north-west and south-east aspects are exported.

When interpreting satellite overlays for quadrant volumes, it is important to note that the contact surface—aligned with the vertical face of the lock—is remapped in this visual output type for improved clarity. To align with satellite imagery captured from directly overhead, the contact surface is rotated upward by 90 degrees about the longitudinal x-axis (Figure 19b).

Figure 19: Diagram showing the relationship between quadrant slice representation on 2D satellite overlays (a) and the in-situ orientation of contact surface (b)

3. River Pilot Test Results

This section provides an overview of surveys carried out within the CRISTAL French pilot on three different locks managed by VNF, i.e.:

- **Survey #1** - Lock 1 (a wide gauge lock on River Seine);
- **Survey #2** - Lock 2 (a narrow-gauge lock on the Canal de la Marne au Rhin);
- **Survey #3** - Lock 3 (another narrow-gauge lock on the Canal de la Marne au Rhin).

The scope of the planned surveys was to acquire measurement data across selected wall quadrants (on Lock 1) and surrounding areas (at all surveyed locks) using the newly developed frame, and pushcart configurations where appropriate. The collected data was then processed and visualised to provide insights into subsurface structural conditions in a range of visual formats, and synchronised with the DT. The surveys also provided an opportunity to assess the practical performance of the SIR system, as outlined in Deliverable D10.1 (CRISTAL, 2025e).

The **specific objectives** were:

- To acquire measurements across multiple wall quadrants (on Lock 1) and surrounding areas (at all locks), with priority given to locations containing suspected or known structural anomalies.
- To generate both 2D and 3D subsurface visualisations for each volume, presented in multiple formats to maximise interpretative clarity.
- To identify and characterise any suspected Fols within each surveyed volume.
- To consolidate and report findings in accordance with requirements of the DT (see Deliverable D5.2) and for infrastructure managers (see Deliverable D8.2).

The following Sections 3.1 to 3.3 present the results of surveys mentioned above, including the context and example of relevant results for each lock.

Finally, Section 3.4 discusses the interpretation of SIR visualisations and their potential applications in maintenance and modernisation practices.

3.1. Survey #1 - Lock 1 (on Seine)

3.1.1. Survey Context and Background

Sub-section 3.1 presents results from the deployment of the developed SIR system between 2nd - 5th December 2024 at a wide gauge lock on River Seine, in Normandy, on the French inland waterways network managed by VNF. For any details not specified below, refer to Deliverable D8.2 (CRISTAL, 2025c).

The lock was selected for three main reasons. First, VNF sought to evaluate the subsurface structural condition of lock wall sections on the north side, particularly near the downstream gate and adjacent gate chamber, including the car park in front of the onsite offices to the north-west. Secondly, the structure was regarded as representative of a typical lock on the network, making it suitable for assessing the overall performance of the SIR system. Thirdly, the lock was scheduled for temporary closure and draining for planned maintenance, providing an ideal opportunity to undertake the survey without disrupting network operations.

The subsurface of lock wall sections and adjacent areas can contain various Fols that may present as signal artefacts in SIR survey data. These include, but are not limited to, man-made culverts

and tunnels for water management, steel reinforcement mesh and rebar for structural stability, and buried utilities such as water, gas, and telecommunications services (Figure 20a). Preliminary consultation with infrastructure managers, combined with technical specifications, highlighted the importance of identifying subsurface voids. These voids typically arise from chemical processes and erosion caused by water ingress into the walls and surrounding ground (Figure 20b). Voids exceeding 100mm in any dimension were noted to be ‘critical’, warranting prompt follow-up to maintain safe and reliable lock operation.

Figure 20: Diagram illustrating: several relevant FoI types (a); photographs showing water discharge from enlarging voids (b); and resulting discoloration of the concrete retaining wall (c)

Figure 21: Visual summary of quadrant scan region placements across lock #1 structure, viewed from the opposite lock side (a); above (b) and annotated with relative separation distances (c)

A total of five independent wall quadrants (Q001–Q005) were surveyed along the northern lock wall, in close proximity to the upstream gate (see Figure 21). The dataset comprised three complete scans and two partial scans, the latter solely of horizontal scan trajectories (Q001-1[^] and Q005-1[^]). A nearby CCTV pole served as a practical positional reference for the frame, supplemented by recorded GPS coordinates. Due to residual water levels following drainage, it was not possible to lower the frame sufficiently to collect data near the base of the lock wall (e.g., Q001-2[^]).

A further five datasets were acquired using the pushcart configuration across selected areas adjacent to the north-west wall quadrants (see Figure 22). These included the combined areas A001-0#, A002-0#, and A003-0# (hereafter collectively referred to as A001-0#), situated beside the lock gate chamber and directly behind Q002-1[^] and Q003-1[^]. These areas exhibited asphalt, brick, and soil contact surfaces, respectively, underlain by moist earth. At the request of the infrastructure managers, the nearby car park - possessing an asphalt contact surface - was also surveyed. This location was suspected to contain one or more large voids associated with a damaged buried drainage channel, although their exact positions were unknown. Finally, A005-0# was surveyed. Of scanned areas, it was recorded in closest proximity to the lock edge over damp, rutted grass, immediately behind the metal covered cable channel running parallel with the lock edge. It represented the most south-easterly dataset recorded during this survey.

Figure 22: Visual summary of area scan region placements about surrounding lock #1 structure, viewed from above (a) and annotated with relative dimensions of extent (b)

Radar measurements across all quadrants were acquired using identical parameter settings. For depth scale previews in Prism2 (separately selected for the SIR geotechnical software), the dielectric model was set to the concrete media preset. Individual 2D transects were recorded at 256 samples per 1D trace without stacking. The scan sounding mode was configured for continuous acquisition, with keystroke triggers applied only at the start and end of each measurement. The antenna type was set to match the 1GHz shielded unit in use, with a 25ns sounding interval for each successive trace. For Prism2 previews, gain was set to 0/36 dB, and a real-time background subtraction filter was enabled. Pulse delay was auto-calibrated prior to the first quadrant scan at 235ps and maintained consistently for all subsequent quadrant measurements.

For surrounding areas surveyed using the pushcart configuration, the dielectric model was set to the soil media preset. Transects were recorded at 512 samples per trace, without stacking. The sounding mode, antenna unit selection, and Prism2 preview settings were unchanged from the

quadrant surveys. The sounding interval was set to 100ns, and a new pulse delay calibration was conducted prior to the first area scan. This was set to 278ps and maintained for all subsequent area measurements.

Environmental conditions ranged from bright sunshine on the first day of measurements to mist and intermittent light rain on subsequent days. Throughout all frame-based scans, the concrete wall surfaces exhibited little discernible surface-moisture across the full vertical range of coverage. In later scans of the surrounding areas on the final day, grass, soil, and asphalt contact surfaces were moderately damp to the touch.

3.1.2. Survey of Lock Walls

This section presents findings from the lock wall quadrant analysis, using a particular relevant example, i.e., **the survey Quadrant Q002-1[^]**. A summary table of findings across all areas is provided in Table 7, and visual outputs and a summary of notable findings for all other SIR surveyed Quadrants are provided in Annex I.

Quadrant Q002-1[^] was positioned directly adjacent to the upstream gate on the northern lock wall (see Figure 23a). The frame was lowered along the wall face, locating the local coordinate origin at 2.2m below the lock edge. This quadrant was of particular interest to infrastructure managers due to its proximity to the lock gate.

From the quadrant's stacked slice (see Figure 23b), no significant Fols were identified within the central region, indicative of a healthy structure. This central subsurface region extended to a depth exceeding 1m and spanned the full longitudinal extent of the frame, vertically extending approximately 0.75m both above and below the frame centre. However, four distinct Fols were identified in the peripheral regions: two near the base of the quadrant, within 0.5m of the frame bottom (Fol-01 and Fol-03), and two near the top, within 0.5m of the frame top (Fol-02 and Fol-04), visible in red. Fol label allocations are shown on the quadrant map (see Figure 24a).

Figure 23: Overlay of surveyed volume Q002-1[^] on satellite map of locks structure (a) and 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #1)

Joint analysis of the stacked slice, corresponding isosurfaces' planar (Figure 24b–c) and isometric projections (Figure 25a), orbital animations (Figure 25b–c), and multislice views (Figure 26) conveyed the relative shape, size, and extent of each Fol. Further characterisation efforts

examined localised footprints through stacked slices spanning the upper and lower interfaces of each FoI (Figure 27), complemented by inspection of signal artefacts observed in the 3D-aligned intersecting transect overlays (Figure 28).

Figure 24: FoI map for surveyed volume Q002-1^ (a) and further 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XZ (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #1)

Figure 25: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume Q002-1^ (a), with representative frames from orbital video shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #1)

Figure 26: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume Q002-1[^], with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #1)

Figure 27: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in Q002-1[^].

Figure 28: Fol spatial profiles for Q002-1[^] with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #1)

Collectively, the identified Fols were estimated to occupy approximately 0.1m^3 of the wall subsurface volume. The leading interfaces of Fol-01, Fol-02, and Fol-03 extended to within 0.25m of the contact surface. Fol-02 was the largest, spanning the full longitudinal extent of the quadrant and reaching to a maximal depth into the subsurface, almost twice that of Fol-01 and Fol-03, with its rear interface reaching nearly 0.5m . Below this, Fol-04 was located directly beneath Fol-02, occupying a region of roughly $0.5\text{m} \times 0.5\text{m} \times 0.25\text{m}$ between $0.7\text{--}0.9\text{m}$ below the contact surface. These Fols exhibited notably irregular boundary interfaces, along with distinctive concentric hyperbolic response profiles in their intersecting transect overlays (i.e., ringing hallmarks), a characterisation consistent with structural defects resembling voids.

A summary table of findings across all quadrants is provided in Table 7 below:

Table 7: Summary of findings across all quadrants surveyed (Lock #1)

Quadrant ID	Total Volume of Fols Identified [m ³]	Quadrant Scan Axis	Description
Q001-1 [^] (see Annex I)	0.1	Mono	Three noteworthy, highly localised Fols identified, with the two largest located at each of the frame's lower corners.
Q002-1 [^]	0.1	Dual	Four noteworthy Fols identified, including a localised 0.7m deep anomaly beneath a larger, shallower anomaly extending across the full longitudinal span of the quadrant to a max depth of 0.5m.
Q003-1 [^] (see Annex I)	0.1	Dual	One noteworthy localised Fol identified at a depth of 0.12m 1.8m horizontally and 1.7m vertically offset from the local coordinate origin.
Q004-1 [^] (see Annex I)	0.0	Dual	No noteworthy Fols identified.
Q005-1 [^] (see Annex I)	0.1	Mono	Three noteworthy Fols, located at depths spanning 0.75–0.9m exhibiting fragmented spatial profiles.

3.1.3. Survey of Lock Surroundings

This section presents findings from analysis of volumes from the lock's surrounding area. A relevant example, i.e., the volume corresponding to surveyed area A004-0# is presented in detail. A summary table of findings across all areas is provided in Table 8, and visual outputs and a summary of notable findings for all other surveyed areas are provided in Annex II.

Area A004-0# encompassed the section of the lock's northern wall car parking area, located approximately 4.2m east of the gate chamber wall (see Figure 29a), with a contact surface measuring 4.0m x 9.3m. The local origin was defined at the intersection of the boundary fences, situated approximately 17.5m directly behind the lock edge (Figure 29b). According to infrastructure managers, the area was suspected to exhibit subsurface degradation associated with a damaged drainage channel, although the precise routing of this channel within the survey area was unknown.

The stacked slice for A004-0# (Figure 29c) highlights the presence of multiple fragmented subsurface Fols across the full extent of the contact surface area, most notably a standalone strong reflector centred longitudinally at approximately 2.9m and transverse at 7.3m relative to the local origin. As in the previous section, labelled Fols are mapped (see Figure 30a) and rendered as planar projections (Figure 30b-c), isometric projections (Figure 31a) and orbitals (Figure 31b-c). In total 6 distinct Fols were identified, all observed to resided at depths between 0.10m and 0.75m as supported by the multislice visuals (Figure 32).

Figure 29: Overlay of surveyed volume A004-0# on satellite map of locks structure from North-West (a) and South-East (b) view angles, alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (c) (Lock #1)

Figure 30: Fol map for surveyed volume A004-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) (Lock #1)

Figure 31: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A004-0# (a), with representative frames from orbital video shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #1)

Figure 32: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A004-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #1)

Fol-03 and the northernmost fragment of Fol-05 were the most sizable standalone anomalies identified, each measuring approximately 1.0m x 1.2m x 0.21m. Fol-04 exhibited the largest overall footprint, extending across the full longitudinal span of the survey area and over 2.3m along

the transverse axis. Although fragmented, an elongated feature linked two sizable anomalies located at local coordinates (2.0, 5.0)m and (3.6, 4.2)m. This linkage, measuring over 2.5 m in total length, exhibited a moderately broad cross-section (Figure 33) and a distorted yet recognisably cylindrical form. Consistently identified at depths of 0.3–0.5 m (Figure 34), these features display characteristics consistent with an old drainage channel.

Figure 33: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A004-0# (Lock #1)

Figure 34: Fol spatial profiles for A004-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #1)

Their form and spatial relationship (particularly relative to the offices to the north-east of the survey area) indicate a likely connection to Fol-03, although this was not directly observed, likely due to occlusion from localised near-surface subsurface heterogeneity given the fragmented form of Fols across this region. An additional alignment appears to extend southwards along the transverse axis towards Fol-05. The larger intervening sections between linkages may also correspond to areas of void development associated with defective channel segments.

A summary table of findings across all areas is provided in Table 8 below:

Table 8: Summary of findings across all surrounding areas surveyed (Lock #1)

Area ID	Total Volume of Fols Identified [m ³]	Description
A001-0# (see Annex II)	0.3	Seven noteworthy Fols identified. Those in A001-0# and A002-0# exhibit a close to random spatial distribution consistent with heterogeneous subsurface conditions, with weaker continuation into A003-0#, while Fol-04 is the only notable standalone feature ($\approx 1 \text{ m} \times 1.5 \text{ m} \times 0.15 \text{ m}$).
A004-0#	0.4	Six noteworthy Fols identified, Fol-03, Fol-04, and Fol-05 were the most sizable anomalies, with the spatial profile of Fol-04 consistent a fragmented drainage channel ($>2.5 \text{ m}$, $0.3\text{--}0.5 \text{ m}$ deep) showing possible void development and interconnections.
A005-0# (see Annex II)	1.2	Five noteworthy Fols identified. Also exhibiting a randomised spatial distribution consistent with a heterogeneous subsurface, with Fol-01, Fol-02, and Fol-03 forming the largest standalone features ($2\text{--}3 \text{ m}$ across, $0.15\text{--}0.7 \text{ m}$ deep).

3.2. Survey #2 - Lock 2 (on the Canal de la Marne au Rhin)

3.2.1. Survey Context and Background

Sub-section 3.2 presents results from the deployment of the developed SIR system on 15th October 2025 at a narrow gauge lock on the Canal de la Marne au Rhin, in the Grand Est region, on the French inland waterways network managed by VNF.

The surveyed lock (Lock 2) was selected for two reasons. First, VNF sought to evaluate the subsurface conditions around the lock's wall sections on both sides of the lock, particularly near the downstream gate. Secondly, the structure was regarded as representative of a typical narrow-gauge lock on the network, making it suitable for assessing the overall performance of the SIR system on this type of lock.

Four datasets were acquired using the pushcart configuration across selected areas adjacent to the lock walls (see Figure 35). These four areas (Lock 2 - A001-0#, A002-0#, A003-0#, and A004-0#) were situated either side of the lock, towards the downstream lock end of the lock. These areas exhibited mostly grass covered soil contact surfaces, with some areas of contact surfaces being concrete, brick and gravel, underlain by moist earth. This location was suspected to have water leaking or infiltrating from the lock into the surrounding soils.

Figure 35: Visual summary of area scan region placements about surrounding Lock #2 structure, viewed from above (a) and annotated with relative dimensions of extent (b)

For the areas surveyed using the pushcart configuration, the dielectric model was set to the soil media preset. Transects were recorded at 512 samples per trace without stacking. The sounding mode, antenna unit selection, and Prism2 preview settings were unchanged from the quadrant and area surveys at Lock 1. The sounding interval was set to 100ns, and the pulse delay was set to 278ps and maintained for all subsequent area measurements.

Environmental conditions throughout the scans were dry with light to moderate cloud cover. Throughout all scans of the surrounding areas the grass covered soil, concrete, brick and gravel contact surfaces were generally dry to the touch.

3.2.2. Survey of Lock Surroundings

This section presents findings from analysis of volumes from the lock's surrounding area. A relevant example, i.e., the volume corresponding to Lock 2 surveyed area A004-0#, is presented in detail. A summary table of findings across all areas is provided in Table 9, and visual outputs and a summary of notable findings for all other surveyed areas are provided in Annex III.

Area A004-0# encompassed the section immediately adjacent to the lock's western wall towards the northern, downstream, end of the lock (see Figure 36a), with a contact surface measuring 21.0m parallel to the axis of the lock by 2.0m in the transverse direction. The local origin was defined in the northeast corner of the area (Figure 36a). According to infrastructure managers, the area was suspected to have water leaking or infiltrating the subsurface from the lock. The stacked slice for A004-0# (Figure 36b) indicates the presence of subsurface Fols concentrated along the long sides of the contact surface area. As in the previous section, labelled Fols are mapped (see Figure 37a) and rendered as planar projections (Figure 37b-c), isometric projections (Figure 38a) and orbitals (Figure 38b-c).

Figure 36: Overlay of surveyed volume A004-0# on satellite map (a), alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #2)

In total, 4 distinct Fols were identified. Fol-01 and Fol-02 are located along the long side of the contact surface area furthest from the lock wall appears to be located in the 0.00-0.20m depth range and are potentially associated with a narrow strip of concrete present at the contact surface along that side of the area. Fol-03 and Fol-04 are located along the long side of the contact surface area closest to the lock wall appears to be located in the 0.20-1.0m depth range, concentrated around 0.50m deep. The estimated size of the Fols in the plane of the contact surface of the area are as follows (the dimensions are listed in order of length along the long axis of the contact surface area that parallels the long axis of the lock, followed by width along the short axis of the contact surface area):

- Fol-01 length 8.6m, width of 0.5m
- Fol-02 length 10.8m, width of 0.5m
- Fol-03 length 2.2m, width variable between 0.25m and 1.0m with an average 0.5m
- Fol-04 length 12.8m, width 0.5m

Considering the shallow depth of Fol-01 and Fol-02 and the presence of a different material at the contact surface to explain the difference in radar returns, these Fol are likely of little significance to the subsurface condition of the structure. Considering the depth and location of Fol-03 and Fol-04 next to the lock wall, these Fol are much more likely to significant to the subsurface condition of the structure, and could indicate regions of void or saturated soils resulting from water infiltration from the lock, although they could represent subsurface features of the lock wall itself. These observations are further supported by the multislice visuals (Figure 39), the slices at the depth of each of the Fols (Figure 40) and the spatial profiles with the intersecting transect scan (Figure 41).

Figure 37: Fol map for surveyed volume A004-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) (Lock #2)

Figure 38: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A004-0# (a), with representative frames from orbits of volume shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #2)

Figure 39: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A004-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #2)

Figure 40: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A004-0# (Lock #2)

Figure 41: Fol spatial profiles for A004-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #2)

While Fol-01 and Fol-02 comprise largely continuous spatial profiles, Fol-03 and Fol-04 appear to be made up of multiple fragmented subsurface spatial profiles that have been considered as continuous Fols as cumulatively they represent a region of interest that exhibit similar properties and could be linked. Additionally, the gaps between the spatial profiles that make up Fol-03 and Fol-04 appear to coincide with location where the transverse scanning transects are further apart, which could indicate that the gaps between the spatial profiles are related to lower scanning resolution at those points, rather than a change in subsurface conditions. The size of the Fols can be judged from their size in the visualisations relative to representation of the transect grid, which is proportional to the size of the contact surface for the area scanned.

A summary table of findings across all areas is provided in Table 9 below:

Table 9: Summary of findings across all surrounding areas surveyed (Lock #2)

Area ID	Total Volume of Fols Identified [m ³]	Description
A001-0#	1.5	Single Fol consisting of a single large continuous spatial profile located along the long side of the contact surface area closest to the lock wall (approximately 13m long by 0.4m wide on average, with a depth range of 0.30-1.0m).
A002-0# (see Annex III)	0.1	Single Fol consisting of a single continuous spatial profile towards the centre of the area of the contact surface with a depth range of 0.20m to 0.50m
A003-0# (see Annex III)	0.2	Single Fol consisting of a single continuous spatial profile towards the centre of the area of the contact surface with a depth range of 0.20m to 0.60m.
A004-0# (see Annex III)	3.7	Four Fols were identified. Fol-01 and Fol-02 are located along the long side of the contact surface area furthest from the lock wall with a depth range of 0.00-0.20m and are potentially associated a narrow strip of concrete. Fol-03 and Fol-04 are located along the long side of the contact surface area closest to the lock wall appears with a depth range of 0.20-1.0m depth range, concentrated around 0.50m deep.

3.3. Survey #3 - Lock 3 (on the Canal de la Marne au Rhin))

3.3.1. Survey Context and Background

Sub-section 3.3 presents results from the deployment of the developed SIR system on 17th October 2025 at another narrow gauge lock on the Canal de la Marne au Rhin, in the Grand Est region, on the French inland waterways network managed by VNF.

The lock, Lock 3, was selected for two reasons. First, VNF sought to evaluate the subsurface conditions along one side of the lock. Secondly, the structure was regarded as a further representative example of a typical narrow-gauge lock on the network, making it suitable for assessing the overall performance of the SIR system on this type of lock as a comparison with the similar narrow-gauge Lock 2 and wide gauge Lock 1.

Two datasets were acquired using the pushcart configuration across selected areas adjacent to the lock walls (see Figure 42) for two areas (Lock 3 - A001-0#, and A002-0#) situated along one side of the lock, with Area A001-0# being immediately adjacent to the southern lock wall, and Area A002-0# being parallel to Area A001-0#, separated from it by a wooden fence that prevented the two areas being scanned as one continuous area. These areas exhibited mostly grass covered soil and gravel contact surfaces, underlain by moist earth. This location was suspected to have water leaking or infiltrating from the lock into the surrounding soils.

Figure 42: Visual summary of area scan region placements about surrounding Lock #3 structure, viewed from above (a) and annotated with relative dimensions of extent (b)

For areas surveyed using the pushcart configuration, the dielectric model was set to the soil media preset. Transects were recorded at 512 samples per trace, without stacking. The sounding mode, antenna unit selection, and Prism2 preview settings were unchanged from the quadrant surveys. The sounding interval was set to 100ns, and the pulse delay was set to 278ps and maintained for all subsequent area measurements.

Environmental conditions throughout the scans were dry with light to moderate cloud cover. Throughout all scans of the surrounding areas the grass covered soil, and gravel contact surfaces were generally dry to the touch.

3.3.2. Survey of Lock Surroundings

This section presents findings from analysis of volumes from the lock's surrounding area. A relevant example, i.e., the volume corresponding to Lock 3 survey area A001-0# is presented in detail. A summary table of findings across all areas is provided in Table 10, and visual outputs and a summary of notable findings for all other surveyed areas are provided in Annex IV.

Figure 43: Overlay of surveyed volume A001-0# on satellite map of locks structure (a), alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #3)

Area A001-0# encompassed the section immediately adjacent to the lock's southern wall along the majority of the length of the lock (see Figure 43a), with a contact surface measuring 24.1m parallel to the axis of the lock by 2.3m in the transverse direction. The local origin was defined at the northwest corner of the area (Figure 43a). According to infrastructure managers, the area was suspected to have water leaking or infiltrating the subsurface from the lock.

The stacked slice for A001-0# (Figure 43b) indicates the presence of a single large subsurface Fol consisting of a mostly continuous spatial profile that extends along the majority of the long side of the contact surface area next to the lock wall, and projects into the volume scanned from the lock wall a distance that is a significant portion of the length of the short side. As in the previous section, labelled Fols are mapped (see Figure 44a) and rendered as planar projections (Figure 44b-c), isometric projections (Figure 45a) and orbitals (Figure 45b-c). The single Fol identified, Fol-01, is located along the long side of the contact surface area closest from the lock wall appears to be located in the 0.20-1.00m depth range and is present consistently throughout that depth range as supported by the multislice visuals (Figure 46).

These observations are further supported by the multislice visuals (Figure 46), the slices at the depth of each of the Fols (Figure 47) and the spatial profiles with the intersecting transect scan (Figure 48). The size of the Fols can be judged from their size in the visualisations relative to

representation of the transect grid, which is proportional to the size of the contact surface for the area scanned.

Figure 44: Fol map for surveyed volume A001-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) (Lock #3)

Figure 45: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A001-0# (a), with representative frames from orbits of volume shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #3)

Figure 46: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A001-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #3)

Figure 47: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A001-0# (Lock #3)

Figure 48: Fol spatial profiles for A001-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #3)

Therefore, the size of Fol-01 can be assessed as being approximately 20m long along the axis of the lock, between 0.6m and 2m wide (average around 0.8m) in the transverse axis of the lock, and up to 0.8m in depth. Considering this size and depth, and it being only 0.2m below the surface, the Fol is unlikely to be a void filled entirely with air or water as in this case the ground surface might be expected to show signs of subsidence into the void, although onsite investigation would be needed to confirm this.

A summary table of findings across both areas is provided in Table 10 below:

Table 10: Summary of findings across all surrounding areas surveyed (Lock #3)

Area ID	Total Volume of Fols Identified [m ³]	Description
A001-0#	17.5	Single large subsurface Fol consisting of a mostly continuous spatial profile that extends along the majority of the long side of the contact surface area next to the lock wall, with a depth range of 0.20m to 1.00m.
A002-0# (see Annex IV)	0.9	Five Fols consisting of groups of multiple fragmented spatial profiles. The majority of the volume of these Fols are in the depth range 0.20m to 0.40m, with some small proportion not in that range being between 0.00m to 0.80m of depth

3.4. Interpretation of SIR Visualisations and Usage in Maintenance Practices and Modernisation

3.4.1. Context: Use of SIR Survey Outputs for Assessing the Assets' Condition

The main scope of developing the SIR system is to enable the improvement of the oversight and maintenance of the condition of IWW assets. The intention is that using the SIR system to capture relevant data would enable the entities in charge of maintenance of IWW assets to better understand the condition of the assets, which would further enable a more effective and efficient implementation of maintenance procedures and processes, i.e., to monitor and maintain the condition of key assets. Furthermore, the use of data collected through surveys using the SIR system would enable IWW infrastructure managers and operators to ensure the reliability, availability, and navigability of IWW cost-effectively. This would support the overall goals for IWW of improving sustainability and market share of IWW, since cost effectiveness and reliability of services are major factors in the attractiveness of a mode of transport, such as IWW to shippers.

The main mechanism by which the use of the SIR system could contribute to improving the reliability and cost effectiveness of IWW would be to enable actions related to maintaining the asset in a functional state, to be more closely aligned with the actual condition of the asset. This is as opposed to waiting for the asset to become non-functional or at apparent risk of failure in the short term (i.e., visually showing obvious signs of issues, e.g., major leaks, partial collapse, etc.), which would require a reactive approach and corrective maintenance. Or, in the case of preventative maintenance, having more detailed information about the subsurface condition from the SIR system could avoid situations where actions appropriate for the potential worst-case condition for any given set of surface indications are decided on due to lack of information on the actual condition, potentially resulting in excessive maintenance to ensure safety and reliability of the asset. For example, if a given set of surface indications that could correspond to either the

case of a minor issue that might remain stable for a number of years, or a serious issue that might lead to a high risk of failure within 6 months, depending on the actual subsurface conditions. Then the uncertainty over the potential for the second case being the current situation might lead to works being planned to prevent the risk of failure. However, if interpretation of the outputs from the SIR system shows that the subsurface condition is expected to be closer to the first, less critical case, then maintenance can be scheduled on longer timescales or deferred without a high risk of failure, which would be less costly for those cases.

3.4.2. Potential integration in maintenance practice

To fully utilise the increased understanding of asset condition that is enabled by data generated by the SIR system, this technology needs to be integrated into the asset maintenance processes, so that the data can be generated when needed and be used effectively to inform the management of maintenance actions for the assets. That is, to use the SIR system to provide an improved understanding of the sub-surface condition of large structures, where information on the condition of the structure has previously been difficult to obtain, and move towards a more condition-based strategy for such critical structures, while maintaining or improving the condition and reliability of assets and the IWW network as a whole.

As stated above, the use of the SIR needs to be integrated into the asset management and maintenance processes for it to be effective. To illustrate how an asset management and maintenance process might be adapted to make use of the SIR system, an overview of the potential integration of the use of SIR into the processes of VNF will be used as an example. This example will compare the high-level overviews of the current maintenance processes (including asset management) of VNF with proposed modifications of the processes to integrate the use of the SIR system.

Currently, the official VNF target for preventive maintenance is to reach 70% of their overall maintenance activities. Compared to corrective maintenance, which is done to repair failures, preventive maintenance is the maintenance done to avoid failures. Repairing is estimated more expensive by VNF and, corrective maintenance can induce an unplanned interruption of traffic, which impacts on operations and revenue, therefore the infrastructure manager aims at avoiding it as much as possible. A more detailed description of the maintenance and asset management processes of VNF can be found in deliverable report D8.1 (CRISTAL, 2024b).

Baseline maintenance practices at VNF

The asset management policy of VNF includes recording the asset on national inventories, including the status of the assets, and definition of Preventive Maintenance Plans and associated operating ranges, on the works. VNF carries out the majority of maintenance, renovation and modernisation work during annual shutdown periods. The status of the asset is monitored as follows.

The asset management process of VNF uses two main methods to determine and monitor the condition of assets, these are:

- National Books Database - The Infrastructure Database (BDO) operational and strategic management tool for VNF's infrastructure assets, data obtained through a [structured/harmonised] "Visit Method" to give a high level overview of the functional state and recommended actions. The BDO is neither a work inspection, nor a diagnosis, nor an exhaustive evaluation of the work to be carried out or a CMMS (Computerised Maintenance Management System).

- Technical Inspection of Assets (VTO) are carried out by persons trained in the inventory, methodology and qualification of VNF's assets. This person is called a Technical Structures Visitor. A "visit" takes between 0.5 to 2 days. It is based on observations (mostly visual) at the time of the visit and on the statements of the operator. During the VTO, no measurements, sampling or tests are carried out. The VTO is not a structural diagnosis. The objective of the VTO is to qualify the functional state of a structure.

Neither of these site visits is described as a detailed inspection of the condition of the structure, or as involving taking measurements related to this. Based on the outcomes of these visits VNF carries out strategic and operational planning of strategic upgrades, and planning of preventative maintenance, as well as any corrective maintenance required in addition to that identified in regular operation.

The technical inspections of assets (VTO) are scheduled based on:

- The Functional Condition Index (FCI), which is determined based on the result of previous inspections (1, 2, 5, or 7 years);
- The works carried out to update the FCI, e.g., repairs, modernisations, etc.;
- Feedback from users or the maintenance service, as well as rounds performed by itinerant staff.

In addition to this, the mobile staff follow their daily route and report any incidents they observe.

Considering all of the above, the current asset management at VNF encompasses the following actions (D8.1, CRISTAL, 2025b):

1. maintenance of assets (discrete and linear works), i.e., all the technical, administrative and management actions during the life cycle of an asset, intended to maintain it or restore it in a state in which it can perform the required function;
2. assets' monitoring, i.e., the activity, carried out manually or automatically, aimed at observing the actual state of the infrastructure; monitoring differs from inspection in that it is used to assess changes in infrastructure parameters over time, being an integral part of asset maintenance;
3. assets' inspection, i.e., the compliance check carried out by measuring, observing, testing or calibrating the significant characteristics of the infrastructure;
4. major maintenance and renewal (GER) of assets, i.e., the action of regenerating part of a piece of equipment or equipment, or the action of major maintenance of long-term equipment, carried out with the aim of increasing the life of the good;
5. assessment of the state of the asset and its monitoring.

The management of documents related to the status and condition of structures is neither centralised, nor accessible to everyone; part of the documents are stored in the project archives, while the other part is digitised and kept within the various departments responsible for the works. Activities are managed through the Computerized Maintenance Management System (CMMS) of VNF Territorial Departments.

The ambition at VNF is to move towards a majority of maintenance actions being preventive and/or predictive, therefore, maintenance plans and operating procedures including details on regular scheduled activities for these structures have been elaborated; however, their implementation remains modest and would need to be enhanced. In this context, the current focus of reactive maintenance is on identifying and managing existing issues.

In terms of the day-to day operation and maintenance of the assets, all structures are connected to the Centralized Control Centres (PCC), which supports the management of the following activities related to operations:

- Hydraulic management of waterway reaches;
- Supervision of the operation of structures;
- User calls in case of difficulties or breakdowns.

Based on this information, the PCC operator takes appropriate measures and records them in the logbook and/or creates a work order in the CMMS. The maintenance staff rely daily on a computer-aided maintenance management application, preventive maintenance plans, and operating procedure to direct them in their maintenance tasks.

Potential improvements of maintenance practices based on use of SIR system

The use of SIR system could be integrated into the asset management procedure as a technique for further investigation after signs of a suspected issue has been detected, or as part of a structural diagnostic prior to defining the restoration/regeneration work program for an asset. Additionally, as part of VNF's current actions to standardize the CMMS across the entire organization. The opportunity could also be taken to integrate non-destructive sub-surface inspection actions into the creation of preventive maintenance plans by type of structure, and to enable the detection of potential defects that are not visible on the surface of the structures.

The information produced by the scans could then be incorporated into the asset management decision making and the Preventive Maintenance Plan (PMP), enabling judgements on the maintenance actions that are required and the priorities of the actions to be made based on an improved understanding of the asset condition. This would also allow the asset condition in asset registers to be more detailed and accurate enabling better decision making regarding strategic upgrades to assets. The expected impact would be improved reliability and availability of the assets due to the detection of issues before they become critical, and improved maintenance efficiency by a reduction unplanned urgent corrective maintenance, and enabling maintenance to be better planned and prioritised in advance according to a better understanding of the asset condition. This includes a potential reduction in unnecessary or low priority maintenance actions undertaken partially as exploratory works due to uncertainty over the extent of issues. The result would be targeted interventions, carried out according to priority, and at the lowest possible cost. The strategic planning of upgrades could also benefit from SIR scans specifically carried out for this purpose, or using information from SIR in the asset register, due to the improved understanding of asset condition enabling better prioritisation of works. Also, due to more accurate estimation of the cost of work required, information from SIR scans could assist in avoiding cost overruns due to unexpected increase in scope of works when discovering unexpected issues with the asset condition during the work.

The main focus of where information from SIR scans could be useful in determining the IWW asset condition and appropriate maintenance actions, include cases where there is structural deformation or evidence of leaks, where the source of the leak in the structure is unclear. In both these cases, information from SIR scans could be potentially useful to IWW managers in pinpointing the source, and determining the extent of the issue, and determining the scope and urgency of maintenance intervention required. This would allow the specification of the work programme for repair or renovation works to be precisely defined.

The further benefits of more efficient maintenance and improved asset reliability to the IWW network as a whole would be the increase in attractiveness of IWW transport to shippers, which

would contribute to increasing revenue for VNF, and overall maintenance cost reductions for VNF. These factors could contribute to economic sustainability of VNF, and/or managing the costs that need to be passed on to shippers to further increase attractiveness of IWW. However, the cost and commercial benefits of using the SIR system would need to be fully assessed based on detailed assessment the costs of operating the SIR system commercially (as opposed to the experimental deployment of the system in the project) and the projected net benefits in terms of reduced maintenance costs and improved reliability of assets.

For example, a hypothetical case study of how the management of a specific issue with the condition of an asset might be dealt with, in the context of using or not using the SIR system is briefly described further. When a potential issue is identified during a VTO, e.g., a crack in the lock wall leaking water into the drained lock, this could be an indicator of a minor surface defect, or of a structural failure of the lock wall and/or a sealing failure leading to water infiltration of the surrounding ground with the potential to cause ground instability. In the case of current VNF inspection practices, maintenance plans and actions would be based mainly on visual inspection, and the visual indications at the surface could be similar for a range of levels of severity of the condition. This could lead to situation of serious structural issues or ground instability being assessed as less critical and urgent than it actually is, with potential for failure of the asset or need of urgent corrective maintenance only becoming apparent later. Alternatively, this situation could lead to exploratory, corrective, or planned maintenance being carried out when the level or severity of the issue was less serious, and action could have been deferred in favour of higher priority activities. If integrating the SIR system into the maintenance processes, for the same potential issue with the condition of an asset, at the point in time of the site visit, different scenarios might be in place:

- A prior scan of the asset might be available, which might show evidence of the presence of a defect or not at a prior date, giving an indication of the rate of progress of any defects.
- A record might be created to pay particular attention to that area on the asset when examining the results of future regularly scheduled scans.
- A new scan of the asset, either the whole asset or a targeted area on it might be commissioned. This action might be based on the time since or until the previous or next scan respectively.

In the scenarios above, any evidence in the scan results indicating the presence of cracks or structural defects (and the extent of those) in the lock wall, or voids in the surrounding ground, can be used by those responsible for maintenance decisions to make a more informed assessment of the current condition of the structure and potentially the rate of development of any defects. They would then be better able to determine the appropriate maintenance response, and urgency of that response, before starting any work, and would be better able to plan the extent of that work based on the increased understanding of the condition of the asset.

3.4.3. Potential Use of SIR Data in Modernisation Programmes

The potential use of SIR data in programmes for the modernisation of IWW assets are largely similar to that for maintenance, in that the SIR data could be used to gather better information on the subsurface condition, and thus enable better informed decisions to be made about the works to be undertaken. It is mainly the scale and management of the modernisation projects that are different to maintenance activities. These modernisation projects have a significant budget, rely on a project management assistant, a design office, and external contractors. The organization and resources deployed are well suited to the use of non-destructive inspection techniques prior

to targeted destructive techniques (guided by the non-destructive inspection). There are two main scenarios where better information on the subsurface conditions provided by SIR data could be used, firstly in optimising the prioritisation of structures for modernisation. Secondly, for structures already scheduled for modernisation, enabling more detailed diagnosis of any issues with the structure as well the general subsurface conditions to enable better planning and estimation of the works to be carried out.

Using the SIR data in the first case, optimising the prioritisation of structures for modernisation, is potentially useful, in detecting those structures at greatest risk of failure (in this discussion the term “failure” could include functional failure, structural failure, or any state of the structure that disrupts traffic). Although the criticality of individual structures to IWW operations, and the potential level of disruption to their failure would still need to be considered. That is, structures where the SIR data is interpreted as showing a lower risk of functional failure on a section of the network with high traffic levels might still have higher overall priority compared to a structure with a higher risk of functional failure on a little used section of the network. The potential use of SIR data for prioritising modernisation of structures is seen as a longer term goal, as currently the techniques is still experimental, there are few technicians trained in the collection and interpretation of the data (low capacity for scanning), and few scans have been carried out. Therefore, there is no SIR data for the vast majority of structures that have not been scanned (and it would take significant time and resources to carry out those scans) to compare the few that have been scanned against, to assess which should have higher priority for modernisation. In this situation, the vast majority of structures that have not been scanned can not be ignored when considering which structures should be prioritised, therefore the pre-existing criteria must be used with only limited consideration being given to SIR data where available (such as where SIR data shows any issues detectable at the surface are of relatively minor concern).

Considering the lack of extensive libraries of SIR data of structures for prioritising modernisation works on structures mentioned (the first case) above, the more likely use for the SIR system in modernisation programmes in the shorter term would be to collect data for assessing the sub-surface condition of structures already considered for modernisation (the second case). Furthermore, these assessments would most likely be targeted at specific sections of a structure in order to investigate the source and extent of the sub-surface causes or consequences of issues detected at the surface, particularly where there the cause of the issue is not obvious and is difficult to locate. The SIR data could then be used to help establish the correct protocol for corrective maintenance or corrective measures required as part of the modernisation of the structure, considering the subsurface condition of the structure. However, if SIR data from previous scans of the structure were to be available in the future, this could also be used for this purpose, or to target specific areas of interest for scans specifically to collect information for the modernisation works. In general the potential use of the SIR system and the data it generates for the modernisation of structures already selected for modernisation would be similar to the potential use of the SIR system in maintenance programmes, with similar potential for reducing the risk of cost overruns in modernisation works due to unexpectedly worse sub-surface condition of structures.

In both of the cases discussed above, the availability of technicians trained and experienced in collecting and interpreting the SIR data would be an issue. A potential organisational response to this might be to outsource the collecting and interpreting of the SIR data to an inspection service as part of a public procurement process, rather than developing the required expertise within the organisation of the IWW operator. Regardless of if the collection of the SIR data was to be internal or external to the IWW operator, the resources required for targeted SIR inspection or diagnosis

campaigns, or scanning a large proportion of the structural assets as a matter of course would need to be balanced against the expected benefits in terms of reduced maintenance and modernisation costs, and improved asset reliability. Since the SIR system is still at the experimental stage, further experience of the use of the SIR data, and its value to maintenance and modernisation programmes, as well as the resources would be needed to make an accurate judgement as to where the balance point is.

4. Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

This report details the development of an advanced methodology for visualisation of SIR datasets that can potentially be used to enhance the resilience of inland waterway infrastructure and reduce maintenance costs. It presents a comprehensive methodology for data collection, analytics, feature analysis, and multimedia output generation, together with an in-depth analysis of findings from recent River Pilot tests focused on in-service lock structures. The potential future application of the SIR system and the information from the interpretation of the visualisations is also discussed.

4.1. Visualisation Methodology

The technology utilised enabled acquisition of significant amounts of survey data within the period the SIR system was deployed for scanning, covering significant surface areas surrounding Lock 1, 2, and 3, although coverage was limited to five wall quadrants on Lock 1. Efficiency in future applications could be improved by increasing antenna traversal speed during transect measurements, thereby reducing scan runtimes. One prospective strategy to achieve this would be through mechanical modifications to the positioning system, such as replacing high-torque, low-speed stepper motor–lead screw assemblies with higher-speed, lower-torque DC motors and belt drives.

The quality of visual outputs was primarily influenced by the directionality and density of scan transects, as well as the selection of the isovalue threshold tuning parameter. Quality assurance tests, restricted to unidirectional scan patterns (horizontal or vertical trajectories only), demonstrated a clear reduction in visual clarity in results from unidirectional scan patterns, highlighting the need for dual-axis scan grids. Further investigation is required into the effect of grid density on visualisation quality. A suitable approach would involve selecting an established subsurface region, performing a high-density scan with closely spaced transects (<100 mm), and progressively subsampling the data to generate lower-density grids for cross-comparison.

The iterative bisection method was found to be a reliable and practical strategy for isovalue threshold selection and is currently considered the most effective approach for practical SIR inspection. However, the tuning of additional parameters such as filter and gain cutoff levels required a degree of operator intuition. This challenge is inherent to SIR data processing and is most effectively addressed through the involvement of experienced equipment operators and analysts during both data acquisition and interpretation.

In assessing the practical contribution of each visualisation format, projections of FoI isosurfaces - particularly from isometric viewpoints - together with animations of 2D slices across the full quadrant and orbital videos, provided the clearest and most readily interpretable survey insights. These were complemented by summary and metadata files, both at the individual volume level and for the full structure under inspection. While requiring greater interpretive effort from the end-user, multislices, FoI maps, satellite overlays, and transect intersection visuals were also valuable for contextualising results. If visual outputs were to be streamlined, the omission of multislice data would have the least impact on overall interpretability. Together these visualisations enable the viewer to visualise the dataset (3D array of datapoints from the survey) as three dimensional (3D) features existing in a 3D space, and relate that to the subsurface conditions on and around the real structure in a meaningful way.

The visualisation process demonstrated adequate reliability for the purposes of this survey. However, scaling to larger datasets (e.g., expanding quadrant coverage to span the full structure)

would require greater automation of media generation, as the current workflow relies on manual intervention at each stage, particularly for orbital outputs. The occurrence of bad blocks indicated a likely buffer overflow error within the Prism2 data collection software. This issue may be addressed either by increasing antenna head movement speed during acquisition to avoid exceeding the buffer limit, or through consultation with the software developers to implement a fix or extend the native buffer capacity.

For the identification and characterisation of Fols, a logical next step is the integration of machine learning models to enable more rigorous segmentation, profiling, and extraction of relevant metrics. Effective implementation could substantially enhance both the accuracy and comprehensiveness of outputs. Future system revisions may also consider incorporating lower-frequency antenna heads (e.g., 250MHz, 500MHz) —or enabling easier interchangeability of antennas—to improve the reliability of attaining survey penetration depths of greater than 1m, though with an inherent trade-off in imaging resolution. The compromise between resolution and scan penetration depth, and the associated definition of requirements, could be reevaluated based on the experience with the prototype as to what it is feasible to achieve. This reevaluation could be based on end user feedback as to the relative priority of these aspects of the results. A combined approach employing both low- and high-frequency antennas may provide a practical balance between penetration and resolution.

A recurring challenge in this work was the absence of reliable ground-truth data on the structure of the subsurface under inspection, as the technology developed represents the first practical method for surveying such infrastructure within the waterways network. While simulation provide suitable evidence of visualisation accuracy for the purposes of this work, further refinement efforts would benefit from comparative studies on in-service structures where accurate reference data are available. Recently engineered structures, supported by detailed technical drawings, CAD models from construction, or records from historic invasive inspections (e.g., borescope surveys), would provide an ideal practical test case for such validation.

4.2. Results

Based on the methodology and process described above, visualisations that can be interpreted to provide information regarding the subsurface condition of IWW structures surveyed using the SIR system have been generated. In total, visualisations of scan results for 3 locks have been generated, i.e.:

- Five scans of vertical lock wall contact surfaces, and three scans of surrounding areas for Lock 1
- Four scans of surrounding areas for Lock 2
- Two scans of surrounding areas for Lock 3

Multiple Features of Interest (Fols) were identified and visualised throughout the scan results, and the visualisations enable the size, shape, and location of the identified Fol to be related to the location of the corresponding regions on and around the IWW structures. The interpretation of the patterns of Fols identified appear to coincide with some of the expected failure mechanisms for locks. That is, Fol that potentially correspond to regions of air or water filled voids, or regions of saturated subsurface material extending from next to the lock wall indicating possible leaks from the lock and associated impact on the lock structure.

It was noticed that all the areas scanned next to the lock walls for Locks 2 and 3 (Lock 2 A001-0# and A004-0#, and Lock 3 A001-0#) exhibited large FoI next to and along lock walls. These regions adjacent to the lock walls were all suspected by the infrastructure managers to have issues. This pattern could have two probable causes. The first is that both locks have issues near the areas scanned, such as water leaking through the lock structure into the surrounding areas. The second probable cause is that these locks have a similar subsurface structure (such as a thicker wall structure lower down the wall) that is being detected at depths of 0.5-1m below the ground level. In either case, the recommended next step would be targeted local physical sampling of investigation of the subsurface (by excavation, bore hole, or probe) to confirm the presence of the Fols and the material that they are made up from. The recommended locations to target specifically would be those where the FoI extends furthest from the lock wall indicating either a deviation from the otherwise regular pattern of subsurface structures detected, or the location where the consequences of a possible issue (such as a leak causing subsurface changes) are at the greatest extent.

The other areas scanned surrounding Locks 2 and 3 exhibited Fols that are probably of secondary interest and could potentially correspond to regions of local variation in the material composition of the ground, general variations in the moisture content of the ground, or localised effects of water ingress from the lock. In the case of Lock 1, there was a general pattern of Fols that could indicate water infiltrating the areas around the northwestern portion of the lock walls and potentially flowing generally north through the subsurface; however, this pattern was less distinct than that for Locks 2 and 3. The recommended next step for Lock 1 would be, similar to Locks 2 and 3, further investigation of subsurface conditions targeted on the most significant Fols identified. In all cases, the targeted investigation of the subsurface issues would provide an independent ground-truth comparison of the structure and composition of the Fols as interpreted from the results from the SIR system. However, these interpretations and recommendations should be considered in terms of the inherent characteristics of GPR data, the current stage of development of the SIR system, and the current early stage of development of the process for application of any results interpretation and recommendations from SIR system to decision making. These factors are discussed in the next subsection.

4.3. Considerations for Further Developments and Use of SIR system in Future

In general, despite the potential benefits of information gained from GPR systems, as used by the SIR system, there are some intrinsic limitations that apply to all GPR technology. Depth and resolution of the results is dependent on ***conditions and the relative electrical properties (dielectric constants) of the materials***; this means that sometimes the radar reflection from the boundary between different materials with similar electrical properties is too weak for the change in materials, and, therefore, the objects to be detected. Also, highly reflective materials near the surface can generate strong reflected signals that generate noise that prevents weaker signals from deeper objects from being detected. Furthermore, the results can be affected by the orientation of the GPR antenna to the objects or material boundaries (something scanned with the

antenna parallel to its length appears differently than one scanned perpendicularly), and interference such as electrical signals from nearby equipment. Depth and resolution are also a trade-off related to the frequency of radar antenna used, lower frequencies penetrate deeper but provide lower resolution whereas higher frequencies offer better resolution for shallow targets but penetrate less deeply.

Other inherent limitations are related to the **level of expertise and experience** required for operating GPR systems and interpreting the results reliably, and with the context of the survey (which is different for different applications and locations). The results can be complex and non-intuitive to interpret, and subject expectation bias. Results can also be ambiguous, general GPR data only indicates that there is a change in material and does not characterise the materials, with different types of objects, or changes in material, having similar GPR signatures. Therefore, GPR is most effective when used **in conjunction with complementary data**, such as plans and records for the sites and structures scanned, and other inspection techniques (such as invasive sampling). When this complementary data is absent the interpretation of the GPR data should be treated with the appropriate caution.

Considering the results from the river pilots and the intrinsic limitations that apply to all GPR systems, the next steps for the development of the SIR system and the potential future use of the interpretation of the visualisations should be understood and pursued. In future, once multiple comparisons have been made between ground-truth destructive inspections and SIR scans, a fuller assessment can be made of the interpretation of the Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) data in general, and SIR data in particular, in the context of IWW structures. This assessment would potentially include an analysis of the appropriate degree of confidence that could be placed on assessments of the subsurface conditions of IWW structures based on SIR system results, and how much independent verification of the interpretation of the SIR system would be appropriate in each case. Furthermore, the quality and accuracy of the interpretation of GPR data in general, and of interpretation of the SIR system data in particular, in the context of IWW structures, are expected to be highly dependent on the experience of operators and technicians performing the work. At the current stage of development of the SIR system, and considering the lack of ground-truth information for comparison, this expertise and experience is still being developed. This means that both the expertise and experience in the use of the SIR system in this context, and the knowledge of characteristic properties and issues of IWW structures must be developed further. Therefore, interpretations of SIR data and visualisations should be regarded as indicative only in the short term, until further experience with the technology as applied to IWW structures is developed

In general, the visualisations of the sub-surface features within IWW structures generated by the SIR system can be considered as potentially useful to IWW operators, particularly for giving information that can be interpreted to better understand the cause, scope and extent of defects and failures of IWW structures. Therefore, there is potential significant benefit from integrating the use of the SIR system and the information generated from it into IWW structure maintenance and modernisation procedures. The most useful potential application of the SIR system in the shorter

term is expected to be for providing enhanced information on defects and failures detected by surface level inspections, with this additional information then being used to improve planning of maintenance and modernisation activities. Detection of concealed defects and failures of IWW structures, the existence of which is not apparent to surface inspections, is considered to be of secondary usefulness, particularly in the short term. This is especially the case when taking into account the time and resources that would be needed for a large-scale scanning and data analysis campaign covering the majority of structures, in order for scans of concealed defects and failures to occur and for defects to be detected. It has been noted that a significant challenge for the widescale use of the SIR system in the future would be the availability of technicians trained and experienced in the use of the system, as such IWW operators might consider either developing the capabilities for collecting, analysis, and interpretation of the SIR data within the organisation or outsourcing the tasks to an inspection service.

Following further development and verification of the SIR system, and considering the availability of technicians and that the expected most likely initial application of the technology during the potential early stages of adoption of the SIR system would be the targeted scanning of defects and failures detected at the surface. Then the integration of the SIR system into maintenance and modernisation procedures would initially most likely be to use it to provide improved information on the subsurface conditions of structures identified as in need of maintenance, or scheduled for modernisation, in order to better plan the works. A more detailed assessment of the SIR technology, with respect to its functional and non-functional requirements (e.g., concerning the operability, maintainability, compliance to norms, etc.) has been carried out in WP10 of the CRISTAL project and the outcomes have been reported in deliverable D10.1 (CRISTAL, 2025e).

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Appendices

This section provides supplementary materials to the work presented in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, including the key visual outputs for each survey volume analysed from the River Pilot Test.

Annex I – Additional Outputs for Lock 1 Walls

Visual outputs found in this section pertain to surveyed Lock 1 Quadrants:

- Q001-1[^] (see Figure 49 to Figure 54)
- Q003-1[^] (see Figure 55 to Figure 60)
- Q004-1[^] (see Figure 61 to Figure 63)
- Q005-1[^] (see Figure 64 to Figure 69)

Analysis of visual outputs identified three distinct noteworthy Fols in **Q001-1[^]**. The two largest, each with an approximate footprint of 0.3m x 0.3m x 0.2m, were located within 0.25m of the bottom corners of the scan area, spanning depths of 0.1–0.3m. Multislice visuals also show a profile suggestive of a potential elongated anomaly extending almost the full vertical range of the scan area at a depth of approximately 0.2m, with a footprint of about 0.2m in width. Aside from these localised anomalies, no other significant Fols were detected.

In **Q003-1[^]**, a single noteworthy Fol was identified at approximately 1.8m along the horizontal axis and 1.7m along the vertical axis from the local coordinate system origin, centred about at a depth of 0.12m. Its rotationally symmetric spatial profile, isolated form, and characteristic ringing hallmarks observed in intersecting transects were indicative of a potential subsurface void.

Q004-1[^] exhibited no detectable Fols, indicating a healthy subsurface condition.

In **Q005-1[^]**, only half of the planned vertical coverage was recorded; however, the available data was sufficient to identify three distinct Fols. These were larger than those recorded in Q001-1[^] and Q003-1[^], particularly Fol-03, which had a footprint exceeding 1.0m x 0.75m x 0.25m, spanning depths of 0.75–0.9m. The fragmented forms, surface roughness, and pronounced ringing hallmarks in intersecting transects were consistent with those of a void defect.

Figure 49: Overlay of surveyed volume Q001-1[^] on satellite map of locks structure (a) and 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #1).

Figure 50: Fol map for surveyed volume Q001-1[^] (a) and further 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XZ (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #1)

Figure 51: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume Q001-1^ (a), with representative frames from orbital video shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #1)

Figure 52: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume Q001-1^, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #1)

Figure 53: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in Q001-1^ (Lock #1).

Figure 54: Fol spatial profiles for Q001-1^ with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #1)

Figure 55: Overlay of surveyed volume Q003-1^ on satellite map of locks structure (a) and 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #1)

Figure 56: FoI map for surveyed volume Q003-1^ (a) and further 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XZ (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #1)

Figure 57: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume Q003-1[^] (a), with representative frames from orbital video shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #1)

Figure 58: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume Q003-1[^], with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #1)

Figure 59: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in Q003-1^ (Lock #1)

Figure 60: Fol spatial profiles for Q003-1^ with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #1)

Figure 61: Overlay of surveyed volume Q004-1[^] on satellite map of locks structure (a) and 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #1)

Figure 62: FoI map for surveyed volume Q004-1[^] (a) and further 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XZ (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #1).

Figure 63: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume Q004-1^, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #1)

Figure 64: Overlay of surveyed volume Q005-1^ on satellite map of locks structure (a) and 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #1).

Figure 65: FoI map for surveyed volume Q005-1^ (a) and further 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XZ (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #1)

Figure 66: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume Q005-1^ (a), with representative frames from orbital video shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #1)

Figure 67: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume Q005-1[^], with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #1).

Figure 68: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in Q005-1[^] (Lock #1)

Figure 69: Fol spatial profiles for Q005-1[^] with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #1)

Annex II – Additional Outputs for Lock 1 Surroundings

Visual outputs found in this section pertain to Lock 1 Areas:

- A001-0# (see Figure 70 to Figure 75)
- A005-0# (see Figure 76 to Figure 81)

Collective analysis of scans from surrounding areas consistently revealed numerous highly fragmented, near-surface anomalies (within 0.2m of the contact surface) exhibiting void-like characteristics, including distinct ringing hallmarks. Deeper anomalies were also detected, such as Fol-02 and Fol-04 in A005-0# at depths of approximately 0.4–0.5m, and Fol-07 in A001-0# at depths exceeding 0.85m.

In the collective area earlier termed A001-0#, Fols were predominantly located within the combined boundary of A001-0# and A002-0#. The reduced frequency of such Fols within A003-0# may be attributable to increased signal attenuation when the radar antenna transitioned from relatively dry asphalt and brick contact surfaces to the exposed grass and soil overlaying A003-0#. The distinctly randomised distribution of small fragments comprising the main Fols in A001-0# and A002-0# is indicative of a natural, healthy, heterogeneous subsurface structure. This interpretation is supported by the consistent pattern observed across both full scan areas and by evidence of continuation into A003-0#, inferred from weaker response profiles visible in the stacked slice. The only notable standalone feature in this area is Fol-04, which exhibits the largest footprint among those detected in A001-0# of approximately 1m x 1.5m x 0.15m.

A similarly randomised spatial distribution was observed for the fragmented Fols in A005-0#. Of particular note, Fol-01, Fol-02, and Fol-03 represented the largest standalone Fols identified, each spanning 2–3m in both longitudinal and transverse dimensions. These features occurred at depths ranging from 0.15m to 0.7m beneath the contact surface.

Figure 70: Overlay of surveyed volume A001-0# on satellite map of locks structure from North-West (a) and South-East (b) view angles, alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #1)

Figure 71: Fol map for surveyed volume A001-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #1).

Figure 72: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A001-0# (a), with representative frames from orbital video shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #1).

Figure 73: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A001-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #1)

Figure 74: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A001-0# (Lock #1).

Figure 75: Fol spatial profiles for A001-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #1).

Figure 76: Overlay of surveyed volume A005-0# on satellite map of locks structure from North-West (a) and South-East (b) view angles, alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (c) (Lock #1).

Figure 77: Fol map for surveyed volume A005-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #1).

Figure 78: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A005-0# (a), with representative frames from orbital video shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #1).

Figure 79: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A005-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #1).

Figure 80: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A005-0# (Lock #1).

Figure 81: Fol spatial profiles for A005-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #1).

Annex III – Additional Outputs for Lock 2 Surroundings

Visual outputs found in this section pertain to Lock 2 Areas:

- A001-0# (see Figure 82 to Figure 87)
- A002-0# (see Figure 88 to Figure 93)
- A003-0# (see Figure 94 to Figure 99)

Lock 2 A001-0# has a single FoI that consist of a single large continuous spatial profile located along the along the long side of the contact surface area closest to the lock wall and is approximately 13m long in this direction 0.4m wide on average, and appears to be located in the 0.30-1.0m depth range.

A002-0# and A003-0# both have a single FoI that is similar in character, being a single continuous spatial profile towards the centre of the area of the contact surface. FoI-01 in A002-0# is approximately 0.80m by 0.60m with a depth range of 0.20m to 0.50m. FoI-01 in A003-0# is slightly larger at approximately 0.80m by 1.4m with a depth range of 0.20m to 0.60m. These dimensions define the approximate extremities of the Fols but their shapes do not fill a cuboid of the stated dimensions.

Figure 82: Overlay of surveyed volume A001-0# on satellite map of locks structure (a) alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #2)

Figure 83: Fol map for surveyed volume A001-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #2)

Figure 84: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A001-0# (a), with representative frames from orbits of volume shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #2).

Figure 85: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A001-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #2)

Figure 86: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A001-0# (Lock #2)

Figure 87: Fol spatial profiles for A001-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #2)

Figure 88: Overlay of surveyed volume A002-0# on satellite map of locks structure (a), alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #2)

Figure 89: Fol map for surveyed volume A002-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #2).

Figure 90: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A002-0# (a), with representative frames from orbits of volume shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #2).

Figure 91: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A002-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #2)

Figure 92: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A002-0# (Lock #2)

Figure 93: Fol spatial profiles for A002-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #2)

Figure 94: Overlay of surveyed volume A003-0# on satellite map of locks structure (a), alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #2)

Figure 95: Fol map for surveyed volume A003-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #2).

Figure 96: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A003-0# (a), with representative frames from orbits of volume shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #2)

Figure 97: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A003-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #2)

Figure 98: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A003-0# (Lock #2)

Figure 99: Fol spatial profiles for A003-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #2)

Annex IV – Additional Outputs for Lock 3 Surroundings

Visual outputs found in this section pertain to Lock 3 Areas:

- A002-0# (see Figure 100 to Figure 105)

Lock 3 A002-0# has multiple fragmented spatial profiles that make up five Fols scattered along the long axis of the contact surface area that parallels the long axis of the lock. These Fols are approximately between 1.20m and 4.80m long along the long axis of the area, and between 0.50 and 1.20m along the short axis of the area. The majority of the volume of these Fols are in the depth range 0.20m to 0.40m with some small proportion of the spatial profiles having sections outside of this range at between 0.00m to 0.80m of depth.

Figure 100: Overlay of surveyed volume A002-0# on satellite map of locks structure from North-West (a) and South-East (b) view angles, alongside 2D stacked slice across full domain (b) (Lock #3)

Figure 101: Fol map for surveyed volume A002-0# (a) and 2D projections of recovered spatial profiles in XY (b) and YZ (c) planes, respectively (Lock #3)

Figure 102: Isometric projection of recovered spatial profiles for survey volume A002-0# (a), with representative frames from orbits of volume shown in (b) and (c) at different view angles (Lock #3)

Figure 103: Multislice representation (a) of survey volume A002-0#, with spatial profile overlay (b) (Lock #3)

Figure 104: Stacked slices spanning Fol's identified in A002-0# (Lock #3)

Figure 105: Fol spatial profiles for A002-0# with overlaid, 3D-aligned intersecting transects (Lock #3)